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D.6.5 Agenda for Smart Future Innovation in E-RIHS

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Abstract

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The purpose of this document is to examine the challenges that E-RIHS needs to address to develop into a sustainable infrastructure, as well as the solutions to address these challenges.

The Agenda for Smart Future Innovation in E-RIHS is conceived as an operational document setting out the priorities for the medium- and long-term sustainable development of E-RIHS in relation to the funding opportunities at regional, national and European levels. The aim is to align these priorities with national and regional research and innovation policies.

The priorities are based on the seven challenges identified in the EC staff working document “Sustainable European Research Infrastructures – A call for action”¹. The Agenda is therefore structured into seven chapters that systematically explore the existing E-RIHS documents and strategies and relate them to the priorities.

A further additional chapter explores long-term multi-level funding opportunities, especially by linking the specialisation of E-RIHS National Nodes with the national/regional Research and Innovation Strategy for Smart Specialisation (RIS3).

This Agenda comes at a crucial point in the lifetime of E-RIHS: the E-RIHS Preparatory Phase project having been completed (2017-2020), the ERIC process ongoing, access being carried out through the IPERION HS project (2020-2024), and the E-RIHS Implementation Phase project ongoing (2022-2024).

The work for the preparation of this Agenda was carried out in the frame of IPERION HS project WP 6: Task 6.2 Sustainability: a strategy for smart future innovation based on identification of specialisations across national nodes.

¹ Sustainable European Research Infrastructures – A call for action COMMISSION STAFF WORKING DOCUMENT — Long-term sustainability of Research Infrastructures, European Commission, 2017.

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Abbreviations

Abbreviations	Expansion
ANTECIPA	Associação Nacional de Pesquisa em Tecnologia e Ciência do Patrimôn
ARCHE	Alliance for Research on Cultural Heritage in Europe
ARCHLAB	ARchive LABoratories
CBA	Cost Benefit Analysis
CHARISMA	Characterisation and HARmonisation for Industrial Standardisation of Advanced MATerials
CLARIN	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
COS	catalogue of services
DARIAH	Digitally enabled research and teaching across the Arts and Humanities
DIGILAB	Digital laboratory
DISSCO	Distributed System of Scientific Collections
DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
ERDF	European Regional Development Fund
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
E-RIHS	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
ESIF	European Structural and Investment Funds
ESS	European Spallation Source
Eu-ARTECH	European - Access, research and technology for the conservation of the European cultural heritage
EU-LAC	European Union - Latin America and the Caribbean
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
FCRF	Fondazione Cassa di Risparmio di Firenze
FIXLAB	Fixed laboratory
FORTH	Institute of Electronic Structure & Laser
HLEG	High-Level Expert Group
IAEA	International Atomic Energy Agency
ICCROM	The International Centre for the Study of the Preservation and Restoration of Cultural

	Property
ICOM	International Council of Museums
ICON	Institute of Conservation
IPERION HS	Integrating Platforms for the European Research Infrastructure on Heritage Science
KPI	Key performance indicator
MOLAB	Mobile laboratory
PID	Persistent Identifier
RDSAB	Advisory Board for Regional Development Strategies
RI	Research Infrastructure
RIS	Research and Innovation Strategy
RIS3	Research and Innovation Strategy for Smart Specialisation
RI-VIS	Increasing visibility of research infrastructures
SFIR	Smart Future Innovation Roadmap
SRIA	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
SSHOC	Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud
STEM	Science, technology, engineering, and mathematics
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization

Narrative (technical) description

Introduction

The *Agenda for smart future innovation in E-RIHS* operationalises the strategic directions provided through the E-RIHS Preparatory Phase and the IPERION HS projects, and delivers an actionable plan of activities arranged in seven priorities.

The *Agenda* is built on two basic premises:

(1) For its long-term sustainability, it is crucial to link E-RIHS with the Research and Innovation Strategy for Smart Specialisation;

(2) A *Roadmap for the smart future growth of E-RIHS* needs to be developed, firmly based on the needs of user communities and existing, and new, facilities of recognised excellence.

The final goal is to stimulate synergies and opportunities between E-RIHS and national/regional Smart Specialisation Strategies, thus helping E-RIHS National Nodes to benefit from European Structural and Investment Funds, taking into account recognised excellence at national and regional level.

The *Agenda* identifies the following priorities:

- **Ensuring scientific excellence of E-RIHS (Chapter 1)**

Efficient operation, continuous maintenance, timely upgrades, as well as identification of new cutting-edge facilities relevant to heritage science ensure the quality and transparency of access provision and infrastructure management.

- **Attracting and training E-RIHS managers, operators and users of tomorrow (Chapter 2)**

From training for the purpose of access to provision of education, strategic links with academia has become essential for RIs. The career paths and mobility of facility managers are coming into sharp focus, as is diversification of the user base.

- **Unlocking the innovation potential of E-RIHS (Chapter 3)**

E-RIHS is fast becoming a “supra-national innovation system” in a highly interdisciplinary field with a significant number of stakeholders. This requires a particular approach to innovation on extremely diverse levels, from technology development to innovative conservation and public services.

- **Socio-economic impact of E-RIHS (Chapter 4)**

RIs are crucially embedded not just in the research landscape, but in the society as a whole. However, RIs are meant to have supra-national impact, as well, E-RIHS having a substantial added value in heritage conservation and valorisation. Methodologies and tools are needed to measure and communicate impact.

- **Improved exploitation of data generated by E-RIHS (Chapter 5)**

Beyond FAIRification of the research data, RIs have the responsibility to promote re-use of data for research, innovation and education. This requires not just consistent data management but also e-infrastructures and e-services that foster interoperability, discoverability and reusability of data.

- **Effective governance and long-term sustainability of E-RIHS (Chapter 6)**

Governance, funding and synchronisation of national roadmaps with the E-RIHS roadmap are central to its long-term sustainability. Embedding E-RIHS in national and regional research and innovation policy agendas and promotion of synergies between funding opportunities at the EU and national levels are essential for the sustainability of E-RIHS.

- **E-RIHS international outreach (Chapter 7)**

International relevance and outreach of E-RIHS requires a firm focus on the needs of international users and stakeholders. International visibility is crucial not just in view of sharing best practices and broadening the user pool, but also in terms of strengthening the commitments on national levels.

- **Transversal priority: Boosting E-RIHS capacity to attract ESI Funds (Chapter 8)**

Stimulating synergies between E-RIHS and the 2021-2027 RIS3 of countries and regions supporting E-RIHS will create a window of joint opportunity. Given the role of RIS3 in guiding R&I investment at the local level in the ESIF programming period 2021-2027, a concerted approach will address the needs of regions for access to knowledge and innovation through support for E-RIHS and foster its development based on a place-based approach.

For each specific challenge, this document identifies several concrete objectives and actions for the next 5-year period.

According to the ERIC Forum Implementation Project report, “it is essential to engage effectively and frequently with regional representatives and even include inviting them to participate in the RI governance to ensure better coordination between local and RI strategies.” Within the IPERION HS project, this will be achieved through the **Advisory Board for Regional Development Strategies (RDSAB)**.

This practice will continue within the E-RIHS Implementation Phase project, with the RDSAB advising the National Coordinators’ Committee, and accordingly, with its Chair providing direction to the Director General.

With the involvement and active participation of the RDSAB members, the *Agenda* pursues two main goals.

Goal 1:

To enable a forum (RDSAB) and put in place a process for stimulating synergies and opportunities between E-RIHS and national/regional direct and indirect R&I investment priorities, with a special focus on the investment domains selected by the RIS3 (2021-2027).

Through the proposed process of coordination, duplication of efforts in terms of research and innovation in different Regions will be avoided.

For the national nodes, strong support of the E-RIHS for regional investments into the RI nodes, aligned with the needs of E-RIHS, would represent a key element of policy support.

Goal 2:

To provide guidance for the development and periodic update of a Smart Future Innovation Roadmap for E-RIHS (SFIR), supporting the investment into facilities that (i) are required by user communities and need to be developed; or (ii) are part of the E-RIHS offer but require upgrading/investment to ensure cutting edge services.

The SFIR document would thus support the national nodes, as well as the facilities themselves to bid for funding at regional (e.g. structural funding), national or EU levels. Currently, there is no E-RIHS policy document that could be referred to in the process of alignment of node development and RIS3 and other strategies, which weakens the position of facilities and nodes on national and regional levels, which is a source of weakness.

Part of the motivation for the development of this *Agenda* is that a partnership strategy for smart future innovation is needed. This document thus aims to chart the process through which the E-RIHS strategy for smart innovation is developed within the E-RIHS IP project, aligning most closely with WP4 (Sustainability of E-RIHS). Such an effort would consist of the following

1. Identification of facilities with recognised excellence in the remit of E-RIHS.²
2. Identification of potential new facilities of recognised excellence³.
3. Gap analysis involving national hubs and user communities suggesting as yet unavailable facilities, or upgrades to existing facilities, thus reinforcing the excellence of E-RIHS ERIC and supporting the national nodes in E-RIHS ERIC. Identification of excellence at regional level would improve the possibilities of funding. The first GAP analysis based on research questions/needs of user communities was performed in the framework of IPERION HS project and is presented in Annex 1.

The above would need to be carried out as a continuous process in clear alignment with the E-RIHS Scientific Strategy, the Advisory Board for Regional Development Strategies (RDSAB), the Committee of National Nodes and with continuous participation of users.

² Cf. IPERION HS Access Catalogue

³ Cf. <http://www.e-rihs.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/D8.3-E-RIHS-Services-for-New-Communities-of-Users.pdf>

Chapter 1: Promoting and supporting scientific excellence of E-RIHS

The pan-European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science (E-RIHS) that will be established with the legal form of a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC), will capitalize on the experience and achievements gained from previous integration projects (Labs TECH, Eu-ARTECH, CHARISMA, IPERION CH) and the current IPERION HS. This RI will offer unprecedented research opportunities to a wide range of interdisciplinary scientific communities; it will foster scientific and technological excellence for interpretation, preservation, documentation and management of heritage by offering access to large-scale instruments, portable devices, physical archives, and their associated staff expertise, and will launch the unprecedented Digital platform DIGILAB for digital archives⁴.

Ensuring excellence will favourably connect E-RIHS ERIC with the Research & Innovation Smart Specialisation Strategies (RIS3), as the development of the RI at regional level will be a key instrument in terms of socio-economic return by stimulating research and innovation and concentrating human capital (e.g., training and attracting international researchers and technicians).

The scientific excellence is also a crucial requirement for the long-term sustainability of E-RIHS, in addition to funding, socio-economic impact and innovation. Additionally, scientific excellence is one of the 10 core pillars of E-RIHS⁵ and the principle of the evaluation criteria for participating partners and for granting access to the RI facilities to carry out research projects in all heritage disciplines. The maintenance of a high level of excellence requires a collective effort of all involved actors and must be regularly assessed by domain experts and members of the E-RIHS ERIC Scientific Advisory Board⁶.

Excellence has been a constant in the previous integration projects already mentioned and E-RIHS ERIC will propose additional measures to maintain and increase it in line with recommendations of the European Commission Staff Working Document “Long-term sustainability of Research Infrastructures”⁷. The operational excellence objectives of E-RIHS are:

Objective 1.1: To put in place transparent access policies according with the principles of the “European Charter for Access to Research Infrastructures”⁸. Conditions of access will be defined by an Access Policy, with scientific excellence as a core principle, for implementing effective, robust and systematic evaluation of submitted access requests. This Policy will determine the scope and procedures of access and the process by which proposals are selected through independent international peer-reviewing. Additionally, each facility of E-RIHS will assess the feasibility and security of user-friendly access services^{9,10}.

⁴ E-RIHS, Scientific Strategy, Deliverable D 9.3 – September 23, 2020, <http://www.e-rihs.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/D9.3-E-RIHS-Scientific-Strategy.pdf>

⁵ E-RIHS, Scientific Strategy, Deliverable D 9.3 – September 23, 2020, <http://www.e-rihs.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/D9.3-E-RIHS-Scientific-Strategy.pdf>

⁶ European Commission, Commission Staff Working Document (SWD), Long-term sustainability of Research Infrastructures, Brussels, 26.9.2017

⁷ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, European charter of access for research infrastructures: principles and guidelines for access and related services, Publications Office, 2016, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/524573>

⁸ E-RIHS ERIC, Scientific and technical description. Preparatory document for E-RISH PP

⁹ E-RIHS, Scientific Strategy, Deliverable D 9.3 – September 23, 2020, <http://www.e-rihs.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/D9.3-E-RIHS-Scientific-Strategy.pdf>

¹⁰ European Commission, Commission Staff Working Document (SWD), Long-term sustainability of Research Infrastructures, Brussels, 26.9.2017

Objective 1.2: To ensure excellence-driven access mode that refers to access approval assessed through peer review that exclusively depends on the scientific quality of the application and its relevance to E-RIHS' vision, mission and values. E-RIHS will foster excellence ensuring the support and continuity of short, medium and large-scale research projects, the latter through multiple access visits (to the same facility, to different facilities from the same platform or to different platforms), and will put in place exploratory projects that will enable the joint progression of knowledge on heritage materials. Proposals coming from new users and stakeholders of diverse fields within the Heritage Science domain (Natural Sciences, **Archaeology, Palaeontology and Palaeoanthropology**, Built Heritage, Social Sciences and Humanities) will be considered for access to the best facilities, resources and services, regardless of their origin and affiliation. To maintain a certain ratio of European users, the access policy might include quotas for non-European users¹¹.

Objective 1.3: To implement an effective, robust and periodic systematic evaluation of the RI by establishing international independent panels of external renowned experts that in the document of the European Commission Staff Working Group¹² are named Technical Evaluation and Management Assessment Committees. These Committees will develop guidelines for independent reviewing, to cover the ethical implications, to ensure the state of the art of the services and to advise and periodically review the development of the science agenda and portfolio that guarantee effective response to the requirements of a wide user community^{13,14}.

Objective 1.4: To Implement quality control with qualitative and quantitative key performance indicators (KPIs) to objectively measure excellence. The background for this development is the operational procedures established by the E-RIHS PP project¹⁵. These procedures aim at measuring the level of excellence and quality of the catalogue of services of the current facilities, of prospective new members, of affiliated organisations, and of research projects or proposals that aim at a closer cooperation with E-RIHS. Based on the quality control, the authorized use of the E-RIHS label by the organizations that adhere to E-RIHS core values and ethical principles will generate recognition and establish a reputation of cross disciplinary excellence in Heritage Science.

Objective 1.5: To count on the contribution of training to the excellence dimension of the facilities by offering dedicated programs for users to effectively use and fully exploit RI instrumentation and expert knowledge¹⁶. The HS Academy, established in the framework of IPERION HS, will be at the forefront of training activities with their doctoral summer schools, onsite training camps, webinar series and training modules that will span further than the present IPERION HS environment¹⁷.

¹¹ E-RIHS, Scientific Strategy, Deliverable D 9.3 – September 23, 2020, <http://www.e-rihs.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/D9.3-E-RIHS-Scientific-Strategy.pdf>

¹² European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, European charter of access for research infrastructures: principles and guidelines for access and related services, Publications Office, 2016, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/524573>

¹³ E-RIHS, Scientific Strategy, Deliverable D 9.3 – September 23, 2020, <http://www.e-rihs.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/D9.3-E-RIHS-Scientific-Strategy.pdf>

¹⁴ European Commission, Commission Staff Working Document (SWD), Long-term sustainability of Research Infrastructures, Brussels, 26.9.2017

¹⁵ E-RIHS PP. D2.2 E-RIHS Quality Manual and KPIs

¹⁶ E-RIHS PP. D7.2 E-RIHS Training Strategy

¹⁷ IPERION HS. D7.3 User Forum and Organisation structure and strategy

Objective 1.6: To monitor the services provided by implementing a tracking system that will note users' acknowledgement to the contribution of the RI when publishing and disseminating their results. This should also link to the development of a simple method for acknowledgement and attribution across complex accesses.

In addition to the above-mentioned general criteria of the European Commission¹⁸, other specific best practices for setting objectives will be implemented to promote and support the scientific excellence of E-RIHS ERIC:

Objective 1.7: To develop a partnership strategy for smart future innovation¹⁹ based on identification of areas of excellence and specialisations across national nodes to promote the presence of cultural heritage and Heritage Science in the regional/national Research and Innovation agendas. This objective will be accompanied by a gap analysis involving national hubs and user communities suggesting as yet unavailable facilities, or upgrades to already existing facilities to promote smart investments in infrastructure and knowledge by national hubs or to suggest future new developments, thus maximizing the chances of success of national hubs in their applications for funds (regional, national or international) via Research and Innovation Strategy for Smart Specialisation (RIS3). The IPERION HS project has set up an Advisory Board for Regional Development Strategies (RDSAB) to support those networking activities for sustainability.

Specialization of access will take into account expert knowledge, excellence of the facilities and the associated scientific expertise embodied by its staff (including interdisciplinary, global cooperation, innovation to stimulate the development of Heritage Science, etc.) to deliver an excellent user experience in terms of scientific and technical support via granted access or simple formal consultations. This strategic approach enables duplication of state-of-the-art techniques when they have associated a distinctive specific expertise and it is open to the possibility of creating dedicated working groups with users and providers around certain types of objects or materials while balancing the geographical distribution of the facilities. Selection criteria of the specialization of access nodes will be contrasted with the track record of excellence of the geographic balanced facilities (equipment and associated expertise) and their capacity of training the new users in given specialized services via KPIs²⁰ and with the establishment of synergies among different techniques.

Objective 1.8: To develop data management strategies that include implementation of the FAIR principles, ensuring better availability, access and reuse of research results and scientific data generated by the RI (as open as possible and as closed as necessary) and that open access to software tools. Data management workflow and practices will support users' access to scientific excellence (knowledge, skills and services) through E-RIHS DIGILAB and other established hubs or digital forums^{21,22}.

Table 1 describes the excellence objectives of E-RIHS, the bodies responsible of their evaluation and the procedures and periodicity established for their achievement.

¹⁸ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, European charter of access for research infrastructures: principles and guidelines for access and related services, Publications Office, 2016, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/524573>

¹⁹ E-RIHS PP. D9.4 Innovation Agenda

²⁰ E-RIHS PP. D2.2 E-RIHS Quality Manual and KPIs

²¹ E-RIHS PP. D5.3 Data Curation Policy

²² IPERION HS. D6.1 Data Management Plan for IPERION HS

Table 1: Excellence objectives of E-RIHS

Goal	Basis	Responsibility	Process	Timing/ Periodicity	Supports Agenda Goal
1.1 To put in place transparent access policies	Access policy Peer-review guidelines Feasibility assessment	Access Board Scientific Advisory Board Facilities Central Hub	Revision of access policies and peer-review guidelines	Annually	2
1.2 To ensure excellence-driven access mode	Peer-review guidelines	Scientific Advisory Board Central Hub	Revision of peer-review guidelines	Annually	2
1.3 To implement an effective, robust and periodic systematic evaluation of the RI	Peer-review guidelines	Technical Evaluation and Management Assessment Committee	Revision of peer-review guidelines	Every three years	2
1.4 To Implement quality control with qualitative and quantitative key performance indicators (KPIs)	D.2.2 E-RIHS Quality Manual and KPIs (E-RIHS PP)	Central Hub (Quality Officer)	Revision of KPIs	Annually	2
1.5 To count on the contribution of training	D. 7.2 E-RIHS Training Strategy (E-RIHS PP) D7.3 User Forum and Organisation structure and strategy (IPERION HS)	E-RIHS Heritage Science Academy	Direct consultation	E-RIHS Training strategy to be updated in 2024	2
1.6 To monitor the services provided	OpenAIRE D.2.2 E-RIHS Quality Manual and KPIs (E-RIHS PP)	Central Hub	Direct consultation	Each 6 months	
1.7 To develop a partnership strategy for smart future innovation	D.9.4 Innovation Agenda (E-RIHS PP)	E-RIHS Central Office RDSAB CNN	Scouting opportunities and preparing applications	Each 6 months	1,2
1.8 To develop data management strategies	D.5.3 Data Curation Policy (E-RIHS PP) D6.1 Data Management Plan for IPERION HS D.2.2 E-RIHS Quality Manual and KPIs (E-RIHS PP)	DIGILAB platform Facility/Users Access board	Revision of data curation policy	Annually	2

Chapter 2: Attracting and training E-RIHS managers, operators and users of tomorrow: E-RIHS Heritage Science Academy

The document “Sustainable European Research Infrastructures – A call for action²³” offers a number of avenues for RIs to make themselves more relevant to their users and facility managers alike, from development of links with academic programmes, exploring mobility and secondment opportunities for providers, to development of career opportunities for access scientists, avoiding the RIs from becoming dead ends of career development. In the pre-operational phase of E-RIHS, however, engagement of users as well as development of the heritage science community remain clear priorities. Both are central to the already existing E-RIHS Training Strategy²⁴, however, more effort is required to develop closer links with academic programmes, as well as doctoral and post-doctoral training opportunities for emerging heritage scientists.

Objective 2.1: To strengthen and diversify the opportunities for user involvement

The diversity of E-RIHS user base is extreme and reflects the remit of heritage science and its extreme interdisciplinarity. In addition to the “traditional” STEM and SSH users, IPERION HS is developing user communities by developing links with the fields of archaeology, built environment and palaeontology/palaeoanthropology.

In order for E-RIHS to become and remain relevant to the global target user communities, it is necessary to enable users to feed into gap analyses (Agenda Goal 2), as well as into the development of new training and engagement opportunities. The basis for this development is the IPERION HS D7.3 User Forum and Organisation structure and strategy²⁵, which has also foreseen new ways of user engagement through user consultation. Establishment of the User Forum and of the User organisation (jointly called Heritage Science Academy) are essential tasks within IPERION HS WP7, to be followed through in E-RIHS ERIC.

Objective 2.2: To develop an application-focussed approach in the E-RIHS Catalogue of Services

User feedback points at the need to communicate the Catalogue of Services through the lens of the desired application, not (only) through the facility/instrumental lens. An application tool should be developed that helps users to narrow down the choice of possible facilities according to the planned application/study subject-matter, and it should encompass all four LAB platforms.

Objective 2.3: To further develop and diversify the offer of the Heritage Science Academy

The Heritage Science Academy is developing into a comprehensive offer of training and engagement opportunities: webinars, lectures, summer schools, training camps, user conferences. These are all led/organised from within the IPERION HS/E-RIHS community, as has been foreseen by D7.3 of IPERION HS. The activities within WP7 of IPERION HS currently include a consultation with users that will establish whether the Academy needs to involve a space, whether physical or virtual, for the users to self-organise.

²³ https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/research_and_innovation/research_by_area/documents/swd-infrastructures_323-2017.pdf

²⁴ E-RIHS PP. D.7.2. E-RIHS Training Strategy, <http://www.e-rihs.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/10/ERIHS-Training-Strategy.pdf>

²⁵ <https://zenodo.org/record/5788566/files/IPERION%20HS%20D7.3%20User%20Forum%20Organisation%20structure.pdf>

This would bring significant benefits to E-RIHS as such a body would represent a community of heritage science users ready for direct engagement.

Of particular significance for E-RIHS, as an innovation ecosystem, is that users have the capacity to actively participate in the innovation chain, and significant potential for innovation lies with users evolving into providers. Users may create or refine techniques to a particular type of heritage. Furthermore, contribution of training to scientific excellence of the RI is crucial for success and RI sustainability. Topics include data management workflow, and practices supporting user access to scientific excellence (knowledge, skills and services) through E-RIHS Digital Infrastructures.

Further training opportunities need to be developed through the E-RIHS IP project (already planned) and in addition, development of training opportunities for early career researchers through e.g. doctoral courses of Marie Curie training networks, should be developed. To achieve this, it is critical to start developing links with academic institutions active in heritage science education.

Table 2 describes the training objectives of E-RIHS, the bodies responsible of their evaluation and the procedures and periodicity established for their achievement.

Table 2: Training objectives of E-RIHS

Goal	Basis	Responsibility	Process	Timing/ Periodicity	Supports Goal	Agenda
Objective 2.1: To strengthen and diversify the opportunities for user involvement	IPERION HS D7.3 User Forum and Organisation structure and strategy	E-RIHS Heritage Science Academy	Direct consultation	Annually	1, 2	
Objective 2.2: To develop an application-focussed approach in the E-RIHS Catalogue of Services	User feedback	E-RIHS Central Office	In consultation between LAB coordinators and facility managers	With each Catalogue of Services	1, 2	
Objective 2.3: To further develop and diversify the Heritage Science Academy	IPERION HS D7.3 User Forum and Organisation structure and strategy	E-RIHS Heritage Science Academy	Direct consultation	E-RIHS Training strategy to be updated in 2024	2	

Chapter 3: Unlocking the Innovation Potential of E-RIHS

E-RIHS is fast becoming a “supra-national innovation system” in a highly interdisciplinary field with a significant number of stakeholders. A major ambition of E-RIHS is to promote a culture of innovation all across the spectrum of its activities: in the context of supporting frontier research, via its diverse access services, through its unique training activities, by building strong links with industrial partners and the broader heritage industry and even at the management level, exploring new models for maximising the impact of HS research on scientific knowledge, technological know-how and socio-economic growth based on the sustainable use of our cultural heritage.

It is quite evident to the community that diverse types of innovations have been and are being developed in the context of the E-RIHS ecosystem, nonetheless it is commonly admitted that innovation examples, successfully exploited by E-RIHS partners, are disproportionately few in comparison to its potential. This has been a major finding of the Innovation Survey carried out in the context of E-RIHS PP and presented in D9.2²⁶. Likewise, the Interim Report on Innovation Strategy of the IPERION HS project (WP6, Task6.1²⁷) identifies fragmentation and the lack of efficient mechanisms as a major obstacle to the path for exploiting innovation in a constructive manner. These findings suggest that there exist gaps that prevent exploitation and commercialization of innovation produced in the context of HS facilities.

To bridge these gaps, a well-defined plan is needed that will offer methods and routes towards efficient exploitation of the E-RIHS innovation potential. Main components of such a plan will include a number of actions as outlined in the following objectives.^{28, 29}

Objective 3.1: Mapping of key achievements – Identifying emerging needs

Already evident, via a look at the IPERION HS/E-RIHS catalogue of services, major achievements represent instrumentation and technologies, measurement methodologies and protocols, as well as documentation tools and data management procedures. An important aspect to take into consideration is that most of these innovations are continuously assessed and evolving, particularly when they are put into practice, thus a critical factor for this progress is the involvement of users (co-creation). But furthermore, this continuous evolution requires the presence of a mechanism and indicators appropriate for monitoring and evaluating the potential of existing or new ideas and tools, identifying emerging needs and opportunities for innovation.

Important factors that need to be addressed include:

- a) What is it worth exploiting? [Definition of ‘exploitable product’, Identification of product potential];
- b) In what ways could an innovative instrument/method/approach be exploited? [Exploitation plan and methodology, Intellectual property rights];
- c) Which is the potential ‘(heritage) market place’ and how strong its interest? [Identify markets and interest];

²⁶ E-RIHS PP Deliverable D9.2 “Analysis of the Innovation Background”.

²⁷ A. Gibson, WP6-MS7 “Interim report on Innovation Strategy”.

²⁸ E-RIHS PP Deliverable D9.4 “Innovation Agenda”

²⁹ IPERION HS Deliverable D6.2 “Exploitation Plan”

- d) Which would be the expected benefits? What would be their value? [Value chain and profit];
- e) Who could/should undertake the effort of exploitation? [Resources and key partnership(s), Facilitators, Training needs];
- f) What are potential obstacles and inhibitors?

Objective 3.2: Monitoring Innovation – The innovation radar

In response to the key factors listed in 3.1, appropriate procedures and methodologies should be introduced to ensure careful monitoring of all the steps along the innovation pipeline. The concept of an **Innovation radar** is introduced, namely a tool that will detect emerging opportunities in terms of:

- a) key areas for development,
- b) collaboration opportunities,
- c) innovation funding schemes and
- d) potential synergies between stakeholders.

It is of importance that the Innovation radar ‘scans’ not only the landscape within the E-RIHS ecosystem but a much broader range (for example, medical diagnostic technologies, automotive and aerospace, construction and buildings sector or forensics and environment) where relevant ideas and technologies grow. This way, it becomes possible to adapt new tools and methods and introduce them to heritage applications and then exploit them in the Heritage marketplace.

Objective 3.3: Facilitating and promoting innovation – Lowering barriers

Along the pathway for generating, promoting and eventually exploiting innovation, a number of key critical issues require thorough attention. These include among others:

- a) the ability to support effectively outstanding research addressing key challenges and needs to ensure rapid progress;
- b) the development of good practices for co-creation (engaging the community of users) and exploitation;
- c) understanding the specifics of the ‘Innovation chain’ in the HS domain;
- d) promoting key synergies and partnerships both within and beyond the HS domain for knowledge exchange and technology transfer and
- e) the ability to identify and exploit channels for funding innovation.

Objective 3.4: Developing key skills and competences

Essential component of the above and of key importance to promoting innovation, is to ensure researchers have the right support that will facilitate them to transfer innovation from the research environment to the Heritage Marketplace. This is not a straightforward process. Appropriate specialized training, particularly for young researchers, is essential for developing skills and competences that will enable them to understand and determine the innovation potential of an idea, a system, a method or a product, search for the right marketplace, identify opportunities and develop a plan for exploitation (including writing a

patents or designing a business plan). In a broader context, these training activities are expected to promote a spirit of creativity, innovation and a transformative, ‘*make it happen*’ culture.

Objective 3.5: Developing a viable Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) Agenda

Careful IPR management is a significant component *en route* to successful exploitation of any innovation capacity. Legal aspects connected to IPRs, on the one hand, and open innovation, on the other hand, are issues that need to be examined across E-RIHS in order to ensure efficient knowledge diffusion without compromising specific rights of individuals (or organizations). Considering the multi-actor nature of E-RIHS (providers, users, support scientists/engineers, etc.) it is important to work towards a well-defined and balanced IP support system, adjustable to the different types of innovations envisaged so as to promote creativity and innovation exploiting the broad knowledge basis in the E-RIHS ecosystem.

Importantly, all of the above relate to the existing national and EU legal and administrative framework for granting and protecting IPRs as well as guidelines and initiatives of international organisations. Recommendations of IPR management practice, guidelines on how to deal with sensitive IPR issues, Creative Commons, Open Access Movement, ethical and other issues related with IPR within E-RIHS have been analysed in the E-RIHS PP deliverable D4.4,³⁰ while additional work is completed in the context of the IPERION HS, WP 6, Task 6.5.

Objective 3.6: Engagement with industrial users

Long-term engagement of the E-RIHS Community with industrial users and other stakeholders sets foundationally favourable conditions for developing innovations and successfully commercialising new technology, services and know-how. This can be facilitated through:

- Adopt a strategic approach concerning the interaction of E-RIHS infrastructures with industrial users and other stakeholders where the latter, beyond access or service receivers, are partners contributing knowledge, complementary expertise, market information, and commercialisation opportunities.
- The establishment of regular connection and consultation sessions (e.g. through meetings, co-creation labs, discussion forums, etc.) between the E-RIHS access providers and industrial users, including SMEs and start-ups. The purpose is to increase industry visibility of research infrastructures and collect input for new product and service ideas and concrete needs from industrial companies. This process not only supports identifying potential users of the infrastructures but contributes to the strategy building of E-RIHS by collecting feedback to support decision-making for new infrastructures and new services.
- Long-term engagement of the Knowledge transfer offices (or industry engagement offices or external relations offices or similar) of the E-RIHS Community with industrial companies, business representative associations such as Chambers of Commerce, tech transfer associations, start-up accelerators, and other multipliers. This process facilitates establishing broader, long-lasting relationships with the business community as it makes access modalities, data management and the IPR management framework clearer to SMEs.

Table 3 describes the innovation objectives of E-RIHS, the bodies responsible of their evaluation and the procedures and periodicity established for their achievement.

³⁰ E-RIHS PP Deliverable D4.4 “IPR management rules”

Table 3: Innovation objectives of E-RIHS

Goal	Basis	Responsibility	Process	Timing/ Periodicity	Supports Agenda Goal
Objective 3.1: Mapping of key achievements – Identifying emerging needs	E-RIHS Catalogue of services D9.3 “Scientific Strategy” (E-RIHS PP) D9.2 “Analysis of the Innovation Background” (E-RIHS PP)	Central Liaison Office for Innovation E-RIHS National Nodes along with associated TTOs RDSAB	Survey and analysis of emerging needs Consultation with the ERIHS Scientific Advisory Board	Annually	1
Objective 3.2: Monitoring Innovation – The innovation radar	D9.4 “Innovation Agenda” (E-RIHS PP) D6.2 “Exploitation Plan” (IPERION HS)	Central Liaison Office for Innovation E-RIHS National Nodes along with associated TTOs	Establishing the Innovation Radar	Continuous action Every three years: Revision of the Innovation Agenda	1
Objective 3.3: Facilitating and promoting innovation – Lowering barriers	D9.4 “Innovation Agenda” (E-RIHS PP) D6.2 “Exploitation Plan” (IPERION HS)	Central Liaison Office for Innovation E-RIHS National Nodes along with associated TTOs RDSAB	Consultation with Regional Governments	Biennially	1
Objective 3.4: Developing key skills and competences	D. 7.2 E-RIHS Training Strategy (E-RIHS PP) D7.3 User Forum and Organisation structure and strategy (IPERION HS)	E-RIHS Heritage Science Academy Central Liaison Office for Innovation	Extension of Training Strategy	E-RIHS Training strategy to be updated in 2024	1
Objective 3.5: Developing a viable Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) Agenda	D4.4 “IPR management rules” (E-RIHS PP) D6.4 “Implementation strategy for IPR management” (IPERION HS)	Central Liaison Office for Innovation E-RIHS National Nodes along with associated TTOs			1

Table 3 continues.

Goal	Basis	Responsibility	Process	Timing/ Periodicity	Supports Agenda Goal
Objective 3.6: Engagement with industrial users	/	Central Liaison Office for Innovation Knowledge transfer office	Adopt a strategic approach concerning the interaction of E- RIHS infrastructure with industrial users and other stakeholders	regular connection and consultation sessions	1

Chapter 4: Socio-economic impact of E-RIHS

The provision of services for advancing Heritage Science (HS) is expected to produce different impacts. They can be split in direct impacts (science production, human capital formation, dissemination and outreach activities) that are directly attributed to E-RIHS ERIC activities and can be measured and generally non-measurable wider impacts, such as science diplomacy and impact on cultural policies, impact on access to culture and on cultural tourism. According to the Cost Benefit Analysis (CBA) performed within the frame of E-RIHS PP project the science production of E-RIHS accounts for 92% of the total quantified impact, while the human capital formation accounts for 4% and the same percentages goes to dissemination and outreach activities³¹. Measuring socio-economic impact of a Research Infrastructure is also one of the key recommendations of the European Commission SWD to ensure the long-term sustainability³².

Objective 4.1: Implementation of the KPIs for impact assessment

A systematic monitoring of the KPIs for impact assessment needs to be assured by the E-RIHS ERIC and evaluation activities, which should be driven by the logic model developed ad-hoc for E-RIHS. This can be done through periodical assessment (via e.g. surveys, specific studies, feedbacks from user groups, etc.) of the impacts of E-RIHS and the satisfaction of its stakeholders. Currently, the measurable core Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that were developed within CBA of E-RIHS PP³³ comprise:

Science Production:

- Number of users of the ERIHS' web portal
- Number of users who access the physical help desk
- Number of users of ARCHLAB, FIXLAB, MOLAB, DIGILAB
- Number of publications
- Number of citations

Human Capital Development:

- Number of Summer Schools attendees
- Number of Training Camps attendees
- Number of Users' Meetings attendees

Dissemination and Outreach:

- Number of users of the ERIHS' web portal
- Number of followers on Facebook
- Number of followers on Twitter
- Number of conferences (events) attendees

Collaboration with industry:

- Number of projects in collaboration with firms/industries
- Number of firms involved in meetings and conferences

The KPIs need to be periodically evaluated and if necessary amended (e.g. a KPI can be added).

³¹ E-RIHS PP D.6.1 Cost Benefit Analysis and socioeconomic impact assessment

³² European Commission, Commission Staff Working Document (SWD), Long-term sustainability of Research Infrastructures, Brussels, 26.9.2017

³³ E-RIHS PP D.6.1 Cost Benefit Analysis and socioeconomic impact assessment

Objective 4.2: Implementation of wider impacts

According to the CBA analysis³⁴ the socio-economic impact needs to be considered as a process rather than as a product of E-RIHS’ activities. To assure high level impact the following actions need to be planned within E-RIHS ERIC:

- 1) A sustainable level of demand aiming at reaching the high number of TNA users of physical platforms should be ensured
- 2) Efforts should be concentrated to create high added-value services for users.
- 3) Contributing to the preparation of a policy agenda for heritage science by adopting a prioritisation mechanism for the identification of the community’s needs should be considered among the internal enabling conditions to make E-RIHS a key actor for heritage science policy.
- 4) The engagement of actors such as SMEs (or their representativeness) and operators in the cultural tourism sector is an additional enabling condition to trigger downstream impacts.

Objective 4.3: Participatory engagement

Public engagement in Heritage Science can additionally raise the general awareness of high added value that Heritage Science can have on cultural heritage, its preservation, cultural tourism and the European identity. This all contributes to long term sustainability of E-RIHS. To reinforce this, Citizens Science projects can be planned. In Heritage science such projects can foresee citizens’ involvement in for example collecting data in a museum or at archaeological site, etc. In addition to already developed KPIs, a KPI is added:

Participatory engagement:

- Number of Citizens Science projects

Audience research³⁵ as a consequence of Citizens Science projects needs to be periodically performed in order to improve the methods of citizens’ engagements and to foster and enrich their experience.

Table 4 describes the socio-economic objectives of E-RIHS, the bodies responsible of their evaluation and the procedures and periodicity established for their achievement.

Table 4: Socio-economic objectives of E-RIHS

Goal	Basis	Responsibility	Process	Timing/ Periodicity	Supports Agenda Goal
Objective 4.1: Implementation of the KPIs for impact assessment	E-RIHS PP D.6.1 Cost Benefit Analysis and socioeconomic impact assessment	E-RIHS Central Office	monitoring and evaluation of the KPIs	Annually	1, 2
Objective 4.2: Implementation of wider impacts	E-RIHS PP D.6.1 Cost Benefit Analysis and socioeconomic impact assessment	E-RIHS Central Office, E-RIHS National Nodes	Direct consultation with users’ groups, engagement with SMEs, HS diplomacy	On-going process	1, 2

³⁴ E-RIHS PP D.6.1 Cost Benefit Analysis and socioeconomic impact assessment

³⁵ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/824711>

Table 4 continues.

Goal	Basis	Responsibility	Process	Timing/ Periodicity	Supports Agenda Goal
Objective 4.3: Participatory engagement	Developing metrics and instruments to evaluate citizen science impacts on the environment and society ³⁶	E-RIHS Central Office	Monitoring of the KPI, Audience research as a consequence of Citizens' Science projects	Annually	2

³⁶ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/824711>

Chapter 5: Improved exploitation of data generated by E-RIHS

As the E-RIHS community transition towards a persistent research community on a European, and international scale, moving away from project-to-project based activities, it will need to be supported by a robust, transparent, integrated, sustainable, digital infrastructure. This infrastructure will need to be built on agreed standards and conventions to support the growth of a worldwide community of researchers and be flexible enough to evolve and exploit future digital developments. To provide long-term, trusted access to Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) research data created and used by E-RIHS, this infrastructure will need to be based on scalable services, open to all, with support for activities in multiple languages, marketing the expertise and opportunities of the E-RIHS community on a global level. To facilitate this, the digital infrastructure will be built on the foundation of a shared use of language, embracing the notions of interoperable linked data, and persistent, citable identification processes, exploiting well supported standard vocabularies, ontologies and systems. The E-RIHS community represents an incredible interdisciplinary group of specialists, and this robust digital infrastructure will foster a shared understanding and integration of opportunities.

Objective 5.1: Create a robust sustainable virtual E-RIHS research community, built around membership to a central digital hub and knowledge base.

In addition to the required political and national membership structure, of the E-RIHS ERIC, further work is also required to foster the growth of the community of researchers on a more individual level. To ensure efficiency and sustainability, this E-RIHS community will need to communicate, interact and work within a common modern digital environment, built on a range of integrated tools and systems, where information, knowledge, and access to services and resources can be shared, referenced, cited and discovered over time.

To sustain this community and provide a strong sense of belonging, researchers will be provided the opportunity to officially join the E-RIHS researcher community by registering with the digital infrastructure and creating unique E-RIHS profiles for themselves within a central digital hub or communications forum, linked, as appropriate, to similar profiles for institutions, research groups, access providers, projects, national nodes, etc. These same profiles will automatically feed into relevant E-RIHS communication channels and clearly indicate each user's level and type of membership, participation within access projects or services, as well as their potential involvement with research interest groups, working groups, committees, boards and the management structures within E-RIHS. These connections will also simplify the process of navigating the complex organisation of E-RIHS and strengthen the transparency of the management of E-RIHS, by giving a clear presentation of who is involved in and responsible for what within the various E-RIHS supported activities.

This digital hub will be the primary access point to E-RIHS for researchers and act as a focus for existing resources and the development of our interdisciplinary community. Acting as a knowledge base, and a starting point to discover further resources such as training materials, a place where questions relating to Heritage Science can be answered or where users can be directed to more dedicated specialist forums. The hub will support best practice and consensus on the use of shared standards (approaches, formats, documents, etc.), helping to present or direct members to practical and appropriate ways and levels of documentation, open access, and publication, across the range of different techniques, experimental procedures and protocols, sampling procedures, data handling, etc., used within Heritage Science. Where

possible, these resources will be developed based on a FAIR unified flexible system of generic models to allow our working practice to evolve and adapt as the work develops.

The E-RIHS digital hub will also bring together details of external tools and services, including data repositories, to provide a single starting point for users. Whether providing direct access to “local” resources or allowing searches to be performed across details pulled from ranges of federated systems. With a strong guiding principle of creating/storing resources once but exploiting and reusing them many times. One E-RIHS membership with one login providing access to a range of tools and services. Data, documents, publications and other resources maintained once in a local or global repository but listed, presented and reused via many portals. Providing access to robust peer-reviewed tools and services, but also listing details of the other community activities - tools being developed, data sets being created, areas of work, and support and service needs. Ensuring that the work we do and how we do it can be as FAIR as the data we publish.

Objective 5.2: Setup key E-RIHS data services including a Vocabulary server, a PID system, and a core E-RIHS data repository for the aggregation of relevant FAIR metadata.

To facilitate the development of a E-RIHS digital infrastructure and to ensure that researchers can reliably exploit the data generated and used by E-RIHS certain key generic digital services and processes will be required. Once setup, these initial digital services are expected to develop over time to match the needs of the E-RIHS community.

Firstly, a Vocabulary server is necessary to ensure that the terms and language used to describe the data generated by E-RIHS are standardized and can be easily understood and interpreted by users across different disciplines, institutions and languages. A Vocabulary server allows for the creation, management, and dissemination of controlled vocabularies that can be used to label and describe the data. This ensures that the data is consistently described and allows for easier discovery and integration with other datasets.

Secondly, a Persistent Identifier (PID) system is necessary to ensure that the data and resources generated by E-RIHS are discoverable and citable over the long-term. PIDs provide a unique, persistent identifier for each dataset, making it easier to locate and cite the data. This is particularly important for the preservation of cultural heritage data, which can have significant value and importance over time.

Finally, a core E-RIHS data repository is necessary for the aggregation of relevant FAIR metadata. The repository will provide a central location for storing and managing the data directly generated by E-RIHS, as well as associated metadata describing FAIR heritage datasets stored in other national or institutional data repositories. This will facilitate the sharing and reuse of the data by other researchers and institutions and help to ensure that the data is FAIR.

In summary, the Vocabulary server, PID system, and core E-RIHS data repository are all essential components of a modern research infrastructure like E-RIHS. They help to ensure that the data generated by E-RIHS is exploitable, by ensuring that it is standardized, discoverable, and reusable over the long-term, which is critical for the advancement of heritage science research.

Objective 5.3: Develop the first iteration of the DIGILAB digital service platform.

A major component of the new E-RIHS digital infrastructure will be the DIGILAB platform, providing guided access to the range of digital tools and services required to process, interpret, publish, archive, and exploit the digital resources created and used across the E-RIHS community.

These tools and services will constitute the fourth branch of services in the E-RIHS catalogue and will be selected in relation to the needs of users and the existing access providers of the other three E-RIHS

platforms, ARCHLAB, FIXLAB and MOLAB. They will range from simple recommended methods of best practice and online tools right up to complex data processing systems making use of high-performance computing systems linked to other infrastructures, such as the EOSC. Some will be automated, supported by clear documentation, whereas others will be based on active collaborations with technical specialists.

All E-RIHS branded services and tools will be peer-reviewed and registered with the Catalogue of Service, but DIGILAB will also allow users to directly collaborate with providers developing new beta tools and services, facilitating access to cutting edge opportunities and supporting the testing, evaluation, development and review of the next generation of tools and services.

As with the other E-RIHS “LABs”, expertise will be key, promoting trust, interoperability, consistency and sustainability, while ensuring that all the required documentation and metadata, related to the provided tools and services and the data they produce, is clearly accessible and linked to any new digital resources produced during the work. This will be key to ensuring that future users can understand and re-use our digital resources and accurately put them in context in relation to new digital resources created in the future.

Objective 5.4: Produce the new E-RIHS Data management plan.

To ensure that the E-RIHS digital infrastructure is accessible to all and that the resources and services offered are FAIR, all working practices will be clearly defined and documented. This will be achieved through the E-RIHS Data Management Plan (DMP), which will act as a general guide outlining key procedures and integrating with relevant large-scale initiatives such as EOSC to ensure sustainability and best practice. The DMP will need to be interoperable with potentially more detailed national, domain, or institutionally specific DMPs that researchers may also need to follow. This will ensure a consistent approach to data management and establish trust in the E-RIHS brand.

The DMP will set out clear minimum requirements for all digital services and procedures, including the use of persistent identifiers (PIDs), data repositories, shared vocabularies, citation and attribution, and digital tools. Recommendations for procedures and best practice will be based on adherence to the FAIR principles and standards, and service requirements for FAIR implementation. E-RIHS will work to aggregate agreed key metadata fields describing resources from disparate repositories to provide a single community search platform.

The DMP will be a living document, evolving with the E-RIHS community, and will grow to include or reference FAIR Digital Object definitions for all techniques in the catalogue of services (COS), simplified data management workflows, and the best supported formats for various forms of data production. The DMP will empower users to access scientific excellence, strengthen interaction and co-creation between E-RIHS and user communities, disseminate innovation, maximize impact, enable the exploitation of results, and promote wider public engagement.

Table 5 describes data exploitation objectives of E-RIHS, the bodies responsible of their evaluation and the procedures and periodicity established for their achievement.

Table 5: Data exploitation objectives of E-RIHS

Goal	Basis	Responsibility	Process	Timing/ Periodicity	Supports Agenda Goal
Objective 5.1: Create a robust sustainable virtual E-RIHS research community, built around membership to a central digital hub and knowledge base.	Ongoing discussions related to digital development of DIGILAB in IPERION-CH, IPERION-HS, E-RIHS PP, E-RIHS IP	E-RIHS Central Office with support from E-RIHS IP WP5	Direct consultation and discussion	Q3/Q4 2023, with ongoing maintenance and support	1 & 2
Objective 5.2: Setup key E-RIHS data services including a Vocabulary server, a PID system, and a core E-RIHS data repository for the aggregation of relevant FAIR metadata.	Ongoing discussions related to digital development of DIGILAB in IPERION-CH, IPERION-HS, E-RIHS PP, E-RIHS IP IPERION-HS M11 Interim report on documentation ... (https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7101168)	E-RIHS Central Office with support from E-RIHS IP WP5	Installation of a well-supported Vocabulary system on a E-RIHS (community) managed or supported serve. Development of an appropriate editorial procedure and board.	Q3/Q4 2023, with ongoing maintenance and support	1 & 2
Objective 5.3: Develop the first iteration of the DIGILAB digital service platform.	E-RIHS IP Grant agreement Ongoing discussions related to digital development of DIGILAB in IPERION-CH, IPERION-HS, E-RIHS PP, E-RIHS IP	E-RIHS IP Task 5.1	Direct consultation and discussion Planned activities within E-RIHS IP WP5	Within the scope of E-RIHS IP	1 & 2
Objective 5.4: Produce the new E-RIHS Data management plan.	D.5.3 Data Curation Policy (E-RIHS PP) D6.1 Data Management Plan for IPERION HS (https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4541266) D.2.2 E-RIHS Quality Manual and KPIs (E-RIHS PP)	E-RIHS IP Task 5.1 E-RIHS Central Office, LAB coordinators and Service Providers	Updating of the existing IPERION-HS DMP and consultation between LAB coordinators	Within the scope of E-RIHS IP and then reviewed annually	2

Chapter 6: Framework for effective governance and sustainable funding in the short-, mid- and long-term scenario

6.1 Effective governance

The effective management of ERIHS needs to be considered in different time plans, characterised by the different objectives.

- The short-term scenario will be focused on the

Objective 6.1.1: To ensure a transparent governance in the transition phase to an ERIC.

A characteristic feature of this period is the parallel operation of several formally independent structures: the interim Governing Assembly (iGA) of ERIHS ERIC and bodies created within infrastructure projects established under Horizon 2020/Horizon Europe. In close cooperation with iGA, precisely defining the division and scope of competencies is necessary. Based on the experience to date, the current division of tasks should be continued, in which iGA focuses primarily on the formal side of ERIC establishment, i.e. the development and adoption of key documents required to establish the ERIC structure by the EC and the founding countries. Activities under Horizon projects should focus on creating practical solutions enabling the effective operation of ERIHS ERIC from the moment of its establishment. To ensure a smooth transition, precise knowledge of the present state of development of national Nodes is critical. A survey dedicated to all active and planned nodes has been issued to gain this information. It concentrates on the following areas:

1. Advance of establishment and structure of the node
2. Legal personality of the Node
3. Characteristic of the Access to facilities – at the national level
4. Budget and sources of financing of the Node
5. Plans for access to the ERIHS ERIC

The survey results will be used to identify the main barriers and difficulties in establishing National Nodes and promote best practices already developed. To help nodes in the integration with ERIC, a workshop dedicated to their leaders will be organised. It will address issues identified from the survey results and other important subjects related to integration like necessary legal transformations, new financing models and more.

- The mid-time scenario This scenario covers the first years of ERIHS-ERIC operation when the infrastructure will operate in its initial configuration, limited to the founding countries and will be focused on the two objectives:

Objective 6.1.2: To expand the group of member countries.

This objective will require defining an access path to ERIC for all interested countries, considering the specificity of national legal regulations. In particular, where needed, support will be provided to enter National Road Maps (by consultations, exchange of experiences, etc.) - see also Chapter 7. To help new members join the infrastructure, a dedicated workshop will be organised to share good experiences and

practices and to resolve specific legal and organisational issues. Furthermore, countries already present on their maps may require similar support for the necessary reporting.

Objective 6.1.3: To make the ERIHS ERIC's offer widely visible.

This objective will require a clear strategy for promoting the ERIHS offer, especially in countries so far not very active in submitting access projects. In parallel, the deep recognition of needs will be necessary, especially by taking into account challenges arising from changes in the physical environment, especially global warming and resultant climate changes, as well as from the socio-economical context of the well-being of objects of cultural heritage like massive tourism, pressure from social media and other difficult to predict factors.

Objective 6.1.4: To maintain the financial stability of the infrastructure.

The concepts leading to this objective are described later in this chapter. Additionally, this scenario comprises also a further implementation of the objectives of the medium-term scenario.

The important role will be given to the Regional Development Strategies Advisory Board (RSDAB). In close cooperation with National Nodes Committee, it should advise on:

1. scouting of prospective national facilities (access providers) to be developed for their participation in the RI,
2. identification of potential National /European resources to enable the implementation of such reinforcements,
3. alignment of national development strategies to support the coherent development of the RI at European level,
4. supporting the implementation at the national level of the resulting agenda for balanced development.

A critical factor in the sustainable development and maintenance of the scientific excellence of the infrastructure is the intelligent development of National Nodes. By this, it is meant a balanced contribution from all partners to the Catalogue of Services based on an analysis of the quality of the offer. This should lead to the definition of narrow, cutting-edge specializations based on a broader provide at the national level – see also Chapter 1.4. This process should also be based on a continuous analysis of the prospective users' needs – see Objective 6.1.3 and Chapter 2.1. National Nodes should also contribute to the following:

1. promotion and dissemination of the offer – in relation to Chapter 4.2
2. promotion of multiple access to building a coherent framework to foster multiple accesses to the same facility, to different facilities of the same platform or the different platforms,
3. fostering interoperability via open science, establishment of a system of support of access of new national nodes.
4. creating a system to support new national nodes in creating their own access offer.

6.2 Sustainable funding

Funding research infrastructure is not the same as funding conventional research projects. For example, it includes the estimation of the costs of constructing, running and updating, the negotiation of participants that involve a political dimension and influence, the close interaction between financing and governance, etc.

Furthermore, research infrastructures have specific features:

- (i) they are lasting initiatives;
- (ii) they evolve according to a decoded lifecycle that includes distinct phases (concept development, design, preparation, implementation, operation, termination), which may have different durations and precise financing requirements;
- (iii) they have a high degree of complexity, especially when it comes to distributed research infrastructure, such as E-RIHS.³⁷

Objective 6.2.1 To implement a sound financial management and accountability for E-RIHS in short-, mid- and long-term scenarios

The sustainable funding of an RI cannot be ensured from the outset for its whole lifetime but has to take into account the short- (1 year), mid- (5 years) and long-term (to 10 years) scenarios in which the RI evolves. To address the overall and long-term financial sustainability of the RI, E-RIHS has developed its business plan based on the E-RIHS STD that is being revised on the basis of the step 1 assessment and will be further elaborated during the implementation phase of E-RIHS (see proposal submitted to Horizon Europe). The business plan deals with both the nature of the activities and the conditions under which they are carried out. It is critical to the proper function of research infrastructure. Its revision from one phase to the next (mid-term) - as it is in the case of E-RIHS - is commonly required and recommended to address better the specific needs of the RI and the changed context in terms of funding opportunities and policies, as well as the scientific requirements. In the mid-term scenario, E-RIHS is dealing with its implementation and operation phases. Funding opportunities to support these phases are provided by the IPERION HS project, which maintains the integrated activities of the E-RIHS community at the translation level, and the E-RIHS IP proposal, which will fine-tune the organization and business model of E-RIHS in view of its further development towards the operational phase. Finally, the short-term scenario implies the preparation of the ERIC annual budgetary exercise that constitutes the time basis upon which financial accountability is organized. For E-RIHS, it will take place starting from the ERIC establishment, expected by the first quarter of 2023.^{38,39}

³⁷ Realising and Managing International Research Infrastructures, <https://www.ceric-eric.eu/project/ramiri-handbook/chapter-4/#anchor12>

³⁸ Realising and Managing International Research Infrastructures, <https://www.ceric-eric.eu/project/ramiri-handbook/chapter-4/#anchor12>

³⁹ E-RIHS ERIC, Scientific and technical description. Preparatory document for Step 1 and Step 2 E-RIHS ERIC submission

Objective 6.2.2 To explore pricing strategy for integration into the E-RIHS financial model

The financial model of E-RIHS has been developed on the basis of the use scenarios and the associated cost models in light of the cost-benefit analysis⁴⁰. The step 1 assessment suggested revising the E-RIHS ERIC cost book and the financial annex taking into account alternative funding mechanisms to support access and reach the financial sustainability of the RI. The opportunity for an RI of providing paid services is foreseen in Art.3 (2) of the Regulation (EC) No 723/2009 on Community legal framework for ERIC that states «*an ERIC shall pursue its principal task on a non-economic basis. However, it may carry out limited economic activities, provided that they are closely related to its principal task and that they do not jeopardise the achievement thereof*». A dedicated working group established in the framework of the (interim) General Assembly of E-RIHS and the E-RIHS IP proposal (Revised Business Plan 2024-2029) are dealing with this matter. However, «*the evaluation of an ERIC will need to consider that the fundamental ambition of an ESFRI RI is well beyond the mere commercial value of its activity: the delivery of non-financially evaluated products, such as scientific breakthrough and education, will remain a paramount remit for an ERIC*»⁴¹.

Objective 6.2.3 To identify and exploit other possible sources of funding

The funding sources of E-RIHS include:

- (i) National funding that could be cash, provided by governmental authorities after the inclusion of E-RIHS in national roadmaps as a result of a negotiation process, and in-kind contributions. It might also include national grants (competitive project-based funding);
- (ii) European funding through direct and indirect financial programs such as Horizon Europe, Digital Europe, the European Regional Development Fund, and the Recovery and Resilience Facility;
- (iii) Revenues that can arise from E-RIHS services as it might be considered in the Revised Business Plan 2024-2029 (E-RIHS IP);
- (iv) Donors: sponsorship of 10 million euros provided by the Fondazione Cassa di Risparmio di Firenze (FCRF) to set up the headquarters of E-RIHS in Florence.

To attract more sources from national and European funding opportunities, E-RIHS will develop a multi-level strategy based on the active involvement of the members of the (interim) Committee of National Nodes and the Advisory Board for Regional Development Strategy (RDSAB). The strategy will include (i) mapping the funding opportunities taking into account the kind of investment in relation to the actions of the E-RIHS STD, vision, and mission (e.g., training, operation, maintaining, and upgrading), (ii) promoting workshop for sharing best-practices, and (iii) encouraging the submission of project proposals by involving the E-RIHS community as required.

The Table 6 below shows an initial mapping exercise in which each E-RIHS action is linked to tentative funding opportunities at the national and European levels.

Table 7 describes sustainable funding objectives of E-RIHS, the bodies responsible of their evaluation and the procedures and periodicity established for their achievement.

⁴⁰ E-RIHS PP D.6.1 Cost Benefit Analysis and socioeconomic impact assessment

⁴¹ EMBRC-ERIC Business Plan Update, 2017

Table 6: Tentative funding opportunities at the national and European levels

E-RIHS ACTIONS	NATIONAL FUNDING (iCNN involvement)	EU FUNDING/Horizon Europe
TRAINING	European Social Funds (ESF), https://ec.europa.eu/esf/main.jsp?catId=576&langId=en	Pillar I – MSCA
TNA, NA, JRA	European Regional Development Fund, https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/atlas/programmes/	Pillar I – RI
UPGRADING	European Regional Development Fund, https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/atlas/programmes/	Pillar I – ERC Pillar II – Cluster (2)
ACCESS	European Regional Development Fund, https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/atlas/programmes/	Pillar I – ERC Pillar II – Cluster (2)
INTERNATIONALISATION		Pillar I – RI dedicated actions
NETWORKING		COST actions, https://www.cost.eu
MANTAINANCE	National funds (national roadmaps)?	
SEVERAL ACTIONS	Recovery and Resilience Facility https://ec.europa.eu/info/business-economy-euro/recovery-coronavirus/recovery-and-resilience-facility_en	

Table 7: Sustainable funding objectives of E-RIHS

Goal	Basis	Responsibility	Process	Timing/ Periodicity	Supports Agenda Goal
Objective 6.2.1 To implement a sound financial management and accountability for E-RIHS in short-, mid- and long-term scenarios	D.11.1 E-RIHS Business Plan v1.01 (E-RIHS PP) E-RIHS Costbook E-RIHS Financial Annex	E-RIHS Governance, i.e., (i)GA, (i)CNN, DG with the technical support of Central Hub	Tabulating annual budget (fees, in-kind contributions, costs) Revision of Business Plan	Annually (ERIC annual budget) Every three years (business plan update)	1, 2
Objective 6.2.2 To explore pricing strategy for integration into the E-RIHS financial model	E-RIHS Scientific and technical description D.6.1 Cost Benefit Analysis and socioeconomic impact assessment (E-RIHS PP)	E-RIHS Governance, i.e., (i)GA, (i)CNN, DG with the technical support of Central Hub	Revision of the Business Plan 2024-2029 under E-RIHS IP	Every three years	2
Objective 6.2.3 To identify and exploit other possible sources of funding	E-RIHS Scientific and technical description	E-RIHS Central Office	Scouting opportunities and preparing project proposals	each 6 months	1, 2

Chapter 7: International outreach strategy of E-RIHS

E-RIHS ERIC will be constituted as a pan-European distributed infrastructure leader in Heritage Science. It will establish strong cooperation and collaboration and will develop funding synergies with European and international organisations, projects and infrastructures^{42,43} to ensure in the long-term its scientific and technological excellence.

The E-RIHS partnership has already established a framework for the development of collaborations with international institutions (mostly via the projects E-RIHS PP and IPERION HS and the ongoing E-RIHS IP), including intergovernmental organisations such as ICCROM, UNESCO and the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA). Private institutions, like the Getty Conservation Institute (USA), The Smithsonian Institution - Museum Conservation Institute (USA), and international associations such as ANTECIPA, Associação Nacional de Pesquisa em Tecnologia e Ciência do Patrimônio (BR) and the JPI on Cultural Heritage, have also acknowledged the global dimension of E-RIHS. Furthermore, there exists links with Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Universidad Nacional de San Antonio Abad del Cuzco, the Israel Antiquities Authority and at European level with CLARIN, DARIAH and CERIC ERICs. Various other projects have developed links and synergies with E-RIHS, among these EU-LAC ResInfra (pilot study with Latin America and Caribbean countries), SSHOC, Europeana, 4CH (for digital transformation) and ARCHE (for the creation of a European alliance in the Heritage Science domain)^{44,45}.

E-RIHS ERIC will fully exploit these synergies, that will be periodically assessed, and will foster further partnerships on the EU scene and beyond, in line with Europe's international cooperation policy objectives and with the European Commission High-Level Expert Group (HLEG) recommendations to strengthen and structure this research area⁴⁶.

Objective 7.1: To further develop a strategy for global dimension of E-RIHS

In the implementation phase of E-RIHS, with support of E-RIHS IP project, collaboration strategies will be defined towards the establishment of common practices and policies with relevant projects and RIs at EU and global level (e.g. CLARIN, DARIAH and CERIC ERICs, DISSCO, SSHOC). Exchanges will take place with different initiatives and infrastructures on ways of functioning in different areas, such as scientific strategy, access protocols, training, communication, dissemination, etc.

A cooperation agreement with ICCROM is already in place for developing advanced training activities, and further actions will be established with the Institute of Conservation (ICON), the International Institute for Conservation of Historic and Artistic Artworks (IIC), the International Council of Museums (ICOM) and the future European Spallation Source (ESS), among others⁴⁷. By fostering these connections, mobility of researches and exceptional training will therefore be promoted on a global dimension.

⁴² E-RIHS IP, Task 4.2 E-RIHS Enlargement strategy

⁴³ E-RIHS IP, Task 6.3 Strengthening E-RIHS ERIC cooperation on the EU scene and beyond

⁴⁴ E-RIHS web page, <http://www.e-rihs.eu/e-rihs-as-a-global-research-infrastructure/>

⁴⁵ E-RIHS ERIC, Scientific and Technical Description. Preparatory document for Step 1 submission to ERIC E-RIHS.

⁴⁶ E-RIHS web page, <http://www.e-rihs.eu/e-rihs-as-a-global-research-infrastructure/>

⁴⁷ E-RIHS, Scientific Strategy, Deliverable D 9.3 – September 23, 2020, <http://www.e-rihs.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/D9.3-E-RIHS-Scientific-Strategy.pdf>

Objective 7.2: To implement provisions for international organizations to become participants and for non-EU partners to become observers

Provisions for the participation of international organizations and for non-EU countries as full partners or observers will be defined throughout the implementation phase of E-RIHS (E-RIHS IP) in the framework of a smart growth strategy that will define the common practices and policies. E-RIHS will integrate new facilities of recognized excellence in Heritage Science (based on quality evaluation) and in base at their capacity to offer in-kind access. Their participation in the future E-RIHS ERIC will be formalised through letters of interest or different kinds of agreements for the role of observer⁴⁸.

Objective 7.3: To align and create synergies with Joint Programming Initiative on Cultural Heritage and Climate Change (JPI CH) and the forthcoming Alliance for Research on Cultural Heritage in Europe (ARCHE)

The New ERA for Research and Innovation⁴⁹ recognises the greatest added value of research infrastructures when used for both research and technology applications. Coherence between European and national levels in R&I priorities and objectives involves recognising and leveraging the value of diversity among MS/AC. The outreach of RIs to other European and national agendas and policies is thus crucial. The Joint Programming Initiative on Cultural Heritage and Climate Change (JPI CH) is a key part of the common vision that the EU and MS/AC share in the research domain of cultural heritage. It is then important that E-RIHS might exploit the full potential of the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) of JPI CH to support the various efforts of the research community to tackle the identified challenges. To this end, JPI CH and E-RIHS should actively encourage the involvement of E-RIHS in the transnational calls for proposals promoted by MS/AC participating in JPI CH. Links between JPI CH and the forthcoming Alliance for Research on Cultural Heritage in Europe (ARCHE) should be made more explicit. The aim is to foster the use of the E-RIHS facilities across the research initiatives supported by the JPI CH and the future European partnership, which ARCHE will hopefully develop in Horizon Europe.

Table 8 describes international outreach objectives of E-RIHS, the bodies responsible of their evaluation and the procedures and periodicity established for their achievement.

Table 8: International outreach objectives of E-RIHS

Goal	Basis	Responsibility	Process	Timing/ Periodicity	Supports Agenda Goal
Objective 7.1 To further develop a strategy for global dimension of E-RIHS	E-RIHS Enlargement strategy E-RIHS collaborative paths traced with other RIs and initiatives at the EU and global level Three white papers produced by the Horizon 2020 RI-VIS project ⁵⁰	E-RIHS Governance, i.e., EB, the RDSAB and the iCNN	Revision of enlargement strategy and collaborative paths	Annually	1

⁴⁸ E-RIHS IP, Task 4.2 E-RIHS Enlargement strategy

⁴⁹ European Commission, The new ERA for Research and Innovation, COM(2020) 628 final, Brussels, 30.9.2020

⁵⁰ ESFRI, ESFRI White Paper 2020. Making science happen. A new ambition for Research Infrastructures in the European Research Area, ESFRI Secretariat, 2020

Table 8 continues.

Goal	Basis	Responsibility	Process	Timing/ Periodicity	Supports Agenda Goal
Objective 7.2 To implement provisions for international organizations to become participants and for non-EU partners to become observers	E-RIHS Enlargement strategy	E-RIHS Governance, i.e., EB, the RDSAB and the iCNN	Revision of the enlargement strategy	Every three years	1
Objective 7.3 To align and create synergies with Joint Programming Initiative on Cultural Heritage and Climate Change (JPI CH) and the forthcoming Alliance for Research on Cultural Heritage in Europe (ARCHE)	E-RIHS collaborative paths traced with other RIs and initiatives at the EU and global level	E-RIHS Central Office	Revision of collaborative paths Joint events to share best practices	Annually	1

Chapter 8: Transversal priority: boosting E-RIHS capacity to attract ESI Funds

The transversal chapter analyses and discusses the existing and potential synergies between the European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science (E-RIHS) and the European Structural and Investment Funds (ESIF), especially by linking the specialisation of E-RIHS National Nodes with the national/regional Research and Innovation Strategy for Smart Specialisation (RIS3).

The main aim is to support E-RIHS National Nodes in benefitting from ESIF opportunities, as a tool to support the ERIHS medium-long term sustainability by taking into account recognised excellences at territorial levels and thus promoting the embedding of E-RIHS with the national and/or regional R&I policy agendas and its socio-economic impact.

The chapter is completed by Annex 2, offering additional information on the key elements and requirements of the Smart Specialisation approach and how the RIS3 European agenda will guide the ESIF R&I investments in the 2021-2027 programming period; and Annex 3, presenting some first evidence of the ongoing mapping and analysis of the 2021-2027 RIS3 of Countries and Regions involved in E-RIHS and its synergies and interrelations with the E-RIHS mission and activities.

Objective 8.1: To raise awareness of the synergic opportunities linking E-RIHS and RIS3

The push to enhance synergies between direct and indirect EU funds is highly stressed by the regulatory framework of the 2021-2027 EU Cohesion Policy (Regulation (EU) 2021/1060). The call for better synergies reflects the need of a more efficient and effective use of available funding instruments to build sustainable long-term knowledge capacities and improve the overall quality of national and regional innovation systems (JRC Technical Reports, 2014). Under the ongoing programming period, the European Commission intends to further promote links and cooperation between ESIF, Horizon Europe and other European programmes related to innovation and thus favour a better alignment of policy instruments, while avoiding, at the same, duplications.

Research Infrastructures (RIs) represent natural candidates for synergies as they involve national/regional research centres in priority disciplines, often trans-territorial, and involve a high budget for planning and implementation (European Commission, 2014).

Synergies can be achieved by sequential and/or simultaneous use of resources. The sequential use of funds refers to both "upstream knowledge capacity" (e.g., ESIF could be used to up-grade a RI, if this supports the socio-economic development of the host region and is in line with the relevant ESIF programmes), and "downstream actions" (e.g., ESIF investment could be used for a better exploitation and dissemination of the results and impacts of RIs) (European Commission, 2014).

In this framework, given the role that RIS3 play in guiding R&I investments at the territorial levels, and especially interventions for the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF), a concerted approach stimulating synergies between E-RIHS and the 2021-2027 RIS3 of involved countries could create a window of joint opportunity.

E-RIHS represents a key international community for boosting excellence and innovation in the interdisciplinary field of Heritage Science. Under the 2014-2020 programming period, cultural heritage has been identified as a RIS3 strategic priority by numerous Regions. Regions identify opportunities in cultural

heritage technologies (e.g., conservation, restoration, monitoring, risk management and environmental protection), digitalisation and imaging; besides, cultural heritage is seen a key element in the development of innovative approaches to tourism and sustainable construction, among the others⁵¹.

The rationale for a stronger collaboration lies in the mutual benefits that it could generate.

On one hand, by including the scheme of regionally anchored RIs in the development of RIS3, Regions can benefit from significant socio-economic local impacts that these generate in terms of access to infrastructures and knowledge, high-quality employment opportunities, and trans-national cooperation. RIs are strongly rooted in the regions and critically influence regional development. The outreach of E-RIHS extends from scientific output to the impact on educational systems, from regional development to overall market effects and general societal benefits, playing a key role in the creation of effective regional innovation systems.

On the other side, E-RIHS can benefit from RIS3 as an additional resource to financially support its implementation and operational phases with particular reference to: up-grade of facilities; enhance human resources quality; provide more efficient or better-quality services for research and professional communities, including local entrepreneurs; foster inter-regional cooperation; and more generally, enhance its territorial dimension according to a place-based approach.

Until now, RIs have not sufficiently included in the planning, design and implementation of the RIS3. A concerted approach would instead address the needs of the Regions for access in knowledge and innovation creation and, at the same time, help E-RIHS to get more actively involved in local development and innovation issues and to find support for its economic sustainability (ERIC Forum Implementation Project, 2019).

Concrete actions could include:

- Contacts with national/regional policy makers responsible for the RIS3 design and implementation;
- Contacts with relevant EU/national/regional public and private stakeholder (e.g., S3 Platform)
- Webinars/workshops dedicated to E-RIHS National Nodes;
- Scientific publications.

Objective 8.2: To promote methods for synergic approaches linking E-RIHS with RIS3

The promotion of interrelations between of E-RIHS and RIS3 requires the development of methods to map and classify, on one side, the research competencies of the different laboratories and services offered by E-RIHS; on the other, the presence of national/regional RIS3 investment priorities related to Heritage Science.

The interdisciplinary character of E-RIHS makes it essential to develop and periodically update a classification system, based on semantic tools, to connect the skills and services of research and innovation of E-RIHS with the opportunities locally offered by the 2021-2027 RIS3 deployment.

⁵¹ <https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/en/home> [visited on January 10, 2023]

Pilot at the Italian level

As a concrete case-study, a pilot under preparation at the Italian level is described. The pilot includes the analysis and classification of E-RIHS national facilities in two phases:

- phase 1: creating a reference ontology for heritage sciences in Italy and classify the research and innovation activities, and services offered by the E-RHIS.it laboratories, with the aim of creating a "semantic" catalogue;
- phase 2: creating a web interface for semantic query and search, to facilitate the exploration of the skills and services offered.

The analysis will be based on semantic techniques that allow to extract concepts and topics from different data sources (e.g., research projects, patents, start up and scientific publications). The semi-automatic nature of these tools allows for providing a snapshot of the state of the art of research and innovation skills in certain areas, and, at the same time, allow a comparative study with other realities.

The definition of the “heritage science” interdisciplinary field will take place through the construction of a domain ontology and will use of the contribution of experts in the domain.

Objective 8.3: To identify specific cooperation areas as best-practices and pilots

Specific cooperation areas can emerge from a deeper analysis of the specific contents of RIS3 domains entailing cultural heritage, including related priorities, specific objectives and financial allocations of the related ERDF 2021-2027 Operational Programs.

This exercise is aimed at identifying the presence of RIS3 investment areas in line with the E-RIHS mission, objectives and needs, thus representing a frame to activate win-win collaborations, which can entail:

- The inclusion of E-RIHS in the local RIS3 consultation process (strategy design/monitoring/review)
- The development of pilots to be implemented at the national or transnational level.

Table 9 describes E-RIHS capacity to attract ESI Funds objectives, the bodies responsible of their evaluation and the procedures and periodicity established for their achievement.

Table 9: E-RIHS capacity to attract ESI Funds objectives

Goal	Basis	Responsibility	Process	Timing/ Periodicity	Supports Agenda Goal	
Objective 8.1: To raise awareness of the synergic opportunities linking E-RIHS and RIS3	E-RIHS Scientific technical description	ERIC, and	(i)CNN, National Nodes, DG, E-RIHS Central Office	Policy-maker and public and private stakeholder engagement	Annually	1
Objective 8.2: To promote methods for synergic approaches linking E-RIHS with RIS3	E-RIHS Scientific technical description	ERIC, and	(i)CNN, National Nodes, DG, E-RIHS Central Office	Mapping, classifying, and matching E-RIHS services with national/regional RIS3 investment priorities	Every three years	1, 2

Table 9 continues.

Goal	Basis	Responsibility	Process	Timing/ Periodicity	Supports Agenda Goal
Objective 8.3: To identify specific cooperation areas as best-practice pilots	E-RIHS Scientific and technical description	ERIC, and (i)CNN, National Nodes, DG, E-RIHS Central Office	Pilots	Every three years	1, 2

Concluding remarks

This document outlines aspects of smart future innovation in E-RIHS and actions that need to be taken in order to assure the sustainability of E-RIHS ERIC. It systematically lists key objectives that need to be periodically addressed in each of the sustainability priorities (scientific excellence, training, innovation, socio-economic impact, data exploitation, effective governance, sustainable funding, international outreach and capacity to attract ESI Funds). This overall systematic approach to the above will ensure success and sustainability of E-RIHS ERIC as a leader in the global HS landscape.

Annex 1: GAP analysis based on research questions/needs of potential E-RIHS users

The GAP analysis was performed through a questionnaire on research questions/needs of potential E-RIHS' users. The questionnaire was addressed to users, who are involved in the broader field of cultural heritage and work across different professional fields, representing a wide range of experts (conservators, restorers, archaeologists, architects, art historians, ethnologists, paleoanthropologists, curators, chemists, biologists, geologists, engineers, etc.). Via the questionnaire, we wished to survey users' research interests and their needs for performing meaningful research in the field of Heritage Science. In the core of the questionnaire we asked participants to list questions (simple or complex) that they would like to explore from their priority area of study and explain them briefly. We received 538 questions, of which some of them have the potential to influence the future research infrastructure development. In order to extract the relevant users' questions and to fully explore research needs of potential E-RIHS' users a further communication with IPERION HS WP7 representatives of users' communities was organised, who ranked the users' questions according to the priorities in their respective fields (SSH, conservation, restoration, archaeology, built environment, palaeontology, etc.). This resulted in 43 relevant research questions (see Table 1) that were further evaluated from providers of future E-RIHS' services. This was performed through iCNN (interim Committee of National Nodes) of E-RIHS with the help of National Coordinators, who made the survey among providers within their National Node, trying to evaluate each of the 43 users' questions from 3 points of view (see Table 1):

A: Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Yes/No/Partially

B: Do you have expertise to answer the question? Yes/No/Partially

C: Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? (Score the importance of the question with the number between 0 (lowest) and 10 (highest))

The Table 1 lists all 43 research questions of potential E-RIHS's users with evaluation of the questions by providers from countries that are currently represented in E-RIHS iCNN (Slovenia, UK, Hungary, Poland, Malta, Cyprus, Portugal, Italy, France, Spain, Belgium, Greece, Romania, and Netherlands).

Table 1: Evaluation of research questions of potential E-RIHS' users. Q: Question; Legend for answers: Y-Yes, N-No, P-Partially.

Question; Legend for answers: Y-Yes, N-No, P-Partially		Slovenia	UK	Hungary	Poland	Malta	Cyprus	Portugal	Italy	France	Spain	Belgium	Greece	Romania	Netherlands
Q1	<i>I am interested in correlating paint layer degradation as a consequence of the wooden support bending</i>														
A	Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Y/N/P	Y	P	P	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	P	P	Y
B	Do you have expertise to answer the question? Y/N/P	Y	P	N	Y	N	P	Y	Y	Y	Y	P	P	P	Y
C	Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? 0 ..10	10	10	2	10	3	8	8	7	9	7	10	9	6	
Q2	<i>We need more models (damage functions) to link environmental data with material degradation and enable evidence-based environmental management.</i>														
A	Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Y/N/P	Y	P	N	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	P	P	Y	P
B	Do you have expertise to answer the question? Y/N/P	Y	Y	N	Y	P	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	P	Y	P
C	Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? 0 ..10	10	10	0	10	7	9	8	10	10	10	10	10	7	10
Q3	How to improve DNA extraction from ancient materials														
A	Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Y/N/P	P	P	N	Y	N	N	Y	N	Y	N	N	Y	P	N
B	Do you have expertise to answer the question? Y/N/P	P	P	N	Y	P	N	Y	N	Y	N	N	Y	P	P
C	Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? 0 ..10	9	8	5	10	5	8	8	5	9	6	0	10	5	10
Q4	I am interested in modelling wind driven rain impacts on building facades														
A	Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Y/N/P	P	P	N	N	N	Y	Y	P	Y	P	P	N	N	N
B	Do you have expertise to answer the question? Y/N/P	P	Y	N	N	P	P	Y	P	Y	P	Y	N	N	P
C	Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? 0 ..10	7	10	0	5	8	9	8	8	7	7	7	2	0	5
Q5	I am interested in the integration/fusion of ground and satellite remote sensing data for the reconstruction of the archaeoenvironment														
A	Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Y/N/P	N	Y	P	N	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	Y	Y
B	Do you have expertise to answer the question? Y/N/P	N	Y	P	N	P	Y	N	Y	P	P	N	Y	Y	P

Question; Legend for answers: Y-Yes, N-No, P-Partially		Slovenia	UK	Hungary	Poland	Malta	Cyprus	Portugal	Italy	France	Spain	Belgium	Greece	Romania	Netherlands
C	Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? 0 ..10	5	10	3	5	8	9	2	9	8	7	0	10	8	
Q6	I am interested in the potential long-term chemical changes in PEG-impregnated archaeological wood and the effects on its mechanical properties. I wonder if there are ways to monitor long-term chemical stability in conserved archaeological wood														
A	Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Y/N/P	Y	Y	N	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y	N	N	P	P	P
B	Do you have expertise to answer the question? Y/N/P	Y	Y	N	Y	N	N	N	P	Y	N	N	N	P	P
C	Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? 0 ..10	6	7	0	10	5	6	7	7	5	6	0	6	6	9
Q7	I am interested in methods to evaluate the effects of different (re-)treatments of archaeological wood.														
A	Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Y/N/P	P	P	P	P	N	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	P	P	P
B	Do you have expertise to answer the question? Y/N/P	P	P	P	P	N	N	Y	P	Y	Y	N	N	P	P
C	Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? 0 ..10	8	8	0	10	6	6	7	8	6	6	0	6	6	9
Q8	I am wondering how machine learning can combine with GIS for archaeological materials?														
A	Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Y/N/P	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	P	N	P	P	P	N	P
B	Do you have expertise to answer the question? Y/N/P	N	Y	N	N	P	Y	N	Y	N	P	P	Y	N	P
C	Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? 0 ..10	5	3	0	6	7	6	6	7	7	8	10	6	5	
Q9	I am interested in the possibility of identifying certain species-specific peptides in animal bone collagen from archaeological sites in order to obtain confirmation of the taxonomic definition of these remains.														
A	Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Y/N/P	P	Y	N	P	N	N	Y	P	Y	P	Y	N	P	N
B	Do you have expertise to answer the question? Y/N/P	P	P	N	P	N	N	Y	P	Y	P	Y	Y	N	P
C	Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? 0 ..10	9	7	5	10	4	8	8	9	8	6	8	9	7	
Q10	I would like to know how to determine the genetic record from the remains of bones of the inhabitants of the Iron Age														
A	Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Y/N/P	N	Y	N	Y	N	N	Y	N	P	P	N	N	N	Y
B	Do you have expertise to answer the question? Y/N/P	N	P	N	Y	P	N	N	N	P	P	N	Y	N	P

Question; Legend for answers: Y-Yes, N-No, P-Partially		Slovenia	UK	Hungary	Poland	Malta	Cyprus	Portugal	Italy	France	Spain	Belgium	Greece	Romania	Netherlands
C	Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? 0 ..10	8	8	0	10	4	8	6	5	8	5	0	10	5	
Q11	I am interested in how diagenesis may affect dating signals in teeth, sediment and speleothems.														
A	Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Y/N/P	P	Y	P	P	N	N	Y	P	P	P	N	N	N	N
B	Do you have expertise to answer the question? Y/N/P	P	P	P	N	N	N	Y	P	P	P	N	N	N	P
C	Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? 0 ..10	8	8	8	10	5	8	8	8	7	6	0	8	5	
Q12	Beyond material heritage, how do audiences engage with multisensory heritage, e.g. olfactory heritage? How do we study, store, archive or reproduce such "objects"? What ARCHLAB facilities are needed to enable this?														
A	Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Y/N/P	Y	P	N	Y	N	N	N	P	N	P	P	N	P	Y
B	Do you have expertise to answer the question? Y/N/P	Y	Y	N	Y	N	N	N	P	N	P	P	N	P	P
C	Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? 0 ..10	9	10	0	10	7	6	3	8	5	6	5	6	5	
Q13	I am interested in understanding old and traditional lining system and recipes														
A	Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Y/N/P	P	Y	P	P	N	N	Y	P	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y
B	Do you have expertise to answer the question? Y/N/P	P	Y	P	Y	P	N	Y	P	P	Y	Y	N	Y	Y
C	Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? 0 ..10	6	6	2	7	7	7	8	6	7	6	8	5	7	8
Q14	Glass and vitreous materials: I am interested in the analysis of altered areas of glass objects for studying specific corrosion phenomena														
A	Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Y/N/P	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
B	Do you have expertise to answer the question? Y/N/P	P	Y	Y	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
C	Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? 0 ..10	10	8	10	10	6	7	8	6	9	10	3	7	8	8
Q15	I am interested in the influence of methyl cellulose on the properties of lime mortars and injection mixtures. Some injection mixtures and mortars available on the market are known to contain methyl cellulose to improve properties. Therefore, I am interested in the advantages and disadvantages of such an injection mixture, or the mortar used in the restoration of wall paintings.														
A	Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Y/N/P	Y	Y	N	P	P	N	Y	Y	Y	P	Y	P	Y	Y
B	Do you have expertise to answer the question? Y/N/P	P	P	N	P	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	P	P	N	Y	Y

Question; Legend for answers: Y-Yes, N-No, P-Partially		Slovenia	UK	Hungary	Poland	Malta	Cyprus	Portugal	Italy	France	Spain	Belgium	Greece	Romania	Netherlands
C	Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? 0 ..10	6	7	0	7	7	7	8	6	7	7	4	5	7	
Q16	I'm interested in development of lightweight systems for the support of detached architectural surface decorations (mosaics, sectilia, wall plaster/painting)														
A	Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Y/N/P	Y	P	N	P	P	P	Y	N	P	Y	Y	N	P	Y
B	Do you have expertise to answer the question? Y/N/P	Y	P	N	N	P	P	Y	P	P	Y	Y	N	P	P
C	Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? 0 ..10	7	6	0	7	7	9	8	7	6	6	6	5	6	
Q17	How do we enable EU-wide evaluation of the heritage capital? We sorely lack hard evidence about the value of heritage and heritage science to support project applications, both nationally and EU-wide.														
A	Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Y/N/P	P	P	N	P	P	N	Y	N	P	P	N	N	P	?
B	Do you have expertise to answer the question? Y/N/P	P	Y	N	P	Y	N	Y	Y	P	P	P	P	P	?
C	Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? 0 ..10	9	10	0	8	7	6	7	9	6	7	7	7	8	
Q18	What is the most suited methodology for the consolidation of degraded wax seals?														
A	Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Y/N/P	Y	Y	N	Y	N	N	Y	N	Y	Y	P	N	P	P
B	Do you have expertise to answer the question? Y/N/P	Y	Y	N	Y	N	N	Y	P	Y	Y	P	N	P	P
C	Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? 0 ..10	6	6	0	9	4	6	8	7	4	6	2	6	6	7
Q19	What would be the best methodology to safely remove degrading PVC lamination from old paper?														
A	Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Y/N/P	Y	Y	P	Y	N	N	Y	P	Y	Y	N	Y	P	P
B	Do you have expertise to answer the question? Y/N/P	Y	Y	P	P	P	N	Y	P	Y	Y	P	N	P	P
C	Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? 0 ..10	6	6	2	10	6	7	8	9	7	7	0	6	7	6
Q20	I am interested in how ancient and traditional linings affect the decay of the original canvases														
A	Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Y/N/P	Y	Y	N	Y	N	N	Y	P	Y	Y	P	N	Y	P
B	Do you have expertise to answer the question? Y/N/P	Y	Y	N	Y	P	N	Y	P	Y	Y	P	N	Y	P
C	Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? 0 ..10	6	6	0	6	6	6	8	6	8	6	8	6	7	8

Question; Legend for answers: Y-Yes, N-No, P-Partially		Slovenia	UK	Hungary	Poland	Malta	Cyprus	Portugal	Italy	France	Spain	Belgium	Greece	Romania	Netherlands
Q21	I wonder if there is a methodology for conservation of concrete monuments														
A	Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Y/N/P	Y	P	N	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	P	P
B	Do you have expertise to answer the question? Y/N/P	Y	Y	N	Y	P	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	P	P	P
C	Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? 0 ..10	10	7	0	10	6	6	8	6	8	9	8	7	7	8
Q22	I am interested in the compatibility of acrylic multilayer paints with other materials in the case of mixed technique works.														
A	Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Y/N/P	P	Y	N	Y	N	P	Y	Y	Y	P	N	N	Y	Y
B	Do you have expertise to answer the question? Y/N/P	P	Y	N	P	N	P	Y	P	Y	P	P	N	Y	Y
C	Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? 0 ..10	6	7	0	9	6	7	8	6	7	7	5	6	7	8
Q23	I am interested in how to preserve typewritten letters on carbon/tissue paper easily prone to laceration														
A	Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Y/N/P	Y	Y	N	Y	N	N	Y	N	P	P	N	N	N	/
B	Do you have expertise to answer the question? Y/N/P	Y	Y	N	P	N	N	N	N	P	P	N	N	N	/
C	Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? 0 ..10	6	7	0	10	4	6	7	5	6	5	0	6	4	
Q24	I'm interested in type and composition of canvas														
A	Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Y/N/P	Y	Y	P	Y	N	P	Y	Y	P	Y	P	N	Y	Y
B	Do you have expertise to answer the question? Y/N/P	Y	Y	P	P	N	P	Y	Y	P	Y	P	N	Y	Y
C	Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? 0 ..10	6	7	2	8	3	8	8	5	4	7	2	6	7	8
Q25	I am interested in conservation-restoration procedures for paper (slowing down acid hydrolysis, oxidative degradation in the case of the use of certain inks and pigments) and related research on degradation and stabilization.														
A	Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Y/N/P	Y	Y	P	Y	P	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	P	P	P	Y
B	Do you have expertise to answer the question? Y/N/P	Y	Y	P	Y	P	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	P	N	P	Y
C	Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? 0 ..10	8	9	4	10	4	7	7	4	9	7	8	7	8	5
Q26	I am interested in modelling indoor air flows near walls and other historic surfaces and morphologies														
A	Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Y/N/P	P	Y	N	Y	P	N	N	P	Y	Y	Y	P	P	N

Question; Legend for answers: Y-Yes, N-No, P-Partially		Slovenia	UK	Hungary	Poland	Malta	Cyprus	Portugal	Italy	France	Spain	Belgium	Greece	Romania	Netherlands
B	Do you have expertise to answer the question? Y/N/P	P	Y	N	Y	P	N	N	Y	Y	Y	P	N	P	P
C	Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? 0 ..10	10	10	0	9	3	6	5	10	10	6	8	6	5	
Q27	I am interested in modelling dust and particulate pollution deposition on historic surfaces														
A	Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Y/N/P	Y	Y	N	Y	N	P	Y	P	Y	P	Y	Y	P	N
B	Do you have expertise to answer the question? Y/N/P	Y	Y	N	Y	N	P	Y	Y	Y	P	P	P	P	N
C	Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? 0 ..10	10	9	0	10	4	8	8	10	10	7	10	7	7	
Q28	I am interested in the impact of construction and technical solutions on the durability of wooden structures?														
A	Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Y/N/P	Y	Y	N	P	N	N	N	P	Y	P	N	N	N	N
B	Do you have expertise to answer the question? Y/N/P	Y	P	N	N	N	N	N	P	P	P	N	N	N	P
C	Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? 0 ..10	8	9	0	9	5	6	6	9	9	5	0	5	3	
Q29	I would like to explore the possibility of quantifying the level of involvement of specific elements or compounds (e.g. sulfate salts, PM2.5-PM10) in stone degradation. Is it possible to estimate with high accuracy and precision the rate of growth of stone degradation products (e.g. black crusts), given quantitative data on the products' composition and air quality measurements?														
A	Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Y/N/P	P	Y	N	N	P	N	Y	P	Y	Y	Y	N	N	N
B	Do you have expertise to answer the question? Y/N/P	P	Y	N	N	P	N	Y	P	Y	Y	Y	P	P	N
C	Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? 0 ..10	6	7	0	9	4	8	7	7	8	9	10	6	4	
Q30	how to develop non-destructive techniques which provide compositional stratigraphical information?														
A	Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Y/N/P	P	P	Y	Y	N	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	P	Y	Y	N
B	Do you have expertise to answer the question? Y/N/P	P	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	P	Y	Y	N
C	Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? 0 ..10	9	9	8	9	4	9	7	9	9	10	8	8	8	
Q31	how develop cleaning materials to limit swelling and leaching?														
A	Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Y/N/P	P	Y	P	P	N	N	Y	P	Y	Y	N	N	Y	N
B	Do you have expertise to answer the question? Y/N/P	P	Y	P	Y	N	N	Y	P	Y	Y	P	N	Y	P

Question; Legend for answers: Y-Yes, N-No, P-Partially		Slovenia	UK	Hungary	Poland	Malta	Cyprus	Portugal	Italy	France	Spain	Belgium	Greece	Romania	Netherlands
C	Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? 0 ..10	7	8	2	9	5	6	7	7	8	7	10	5	7	
Q32	I would like to use robots in the simple tasks of conservators (for example for digitalization, cleaning, etc.)														
A	Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Y/N/P	N	P	N	P	N	N	N	P	P	P	N	P	N	N
B	Do you have expertise to answer the question? Y/N/P	N	N	N	P	N	N	N	P	N	P	N	P	N	N
C	Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? 0 ..10	0	10	0	10	0	4	0	10	8	5	0	7	5	
Q33	I am interested in evaluating how cleaning affects paper or parchment supports in terms of structural changes but also regarding hygroscopic properties of the asset.														
A	Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Y/N/P	Y	Y	N	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	N	Y	P
B	Do you have expertise to answer the question? Y/N/P	Y	Y	N	Y	N	N	Y	P	Y	Y	N	N	Y	P
C	Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? 0 ..10	6	6	0	10	7	6	8	8	7	8	0	8	8	
Q34	Investigate and characterise the media and potential degradation issues of overhead pens and plastic - how and to what are their sensitivities? What are the constituents? How are they affected over time?														
A	Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Y/N/P	Y	Y	N	Y	N	N	N	Y	P	Y	N	N	P	N
B	Do you have expertise to answer the question? Y/N/P	Y	P	N	Y	N	N	N	Y	N	P	P	N	N	N
C	Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? 0 ..10	6	6	0	10	0	5	0	8	4	6	0	5	7	
Q35	I am interested in how to analyse intact objects and materials with mass spectrometry that are too large or fragile for conventional sampling methods.														
A	Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Y/N/P	Y	P	N	Y	N	N	N	P	Y	Y	N	N	P	P
B	Do you have expertise to answer the question? Y/N/P	Y	P	N	Y	N	N	N	Y	Y	Y	N	P	Y	P
C	Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? 0 ..10	8	9	0	9	6	7	7	9	8	7	7	8	7	8
Q36	How to adapt techniques such as SERS in a non-invasive way?														
A	Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Y/N/P	P	P	N	P	N	N	N	Y	N	Y	N	N	N	P
B	Do you have expertise to answer the question? Y/N/P	P	P	N	P	N	N	N	Y	N	Y	N	P	N	P
C	Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? 0 ..11	8	9	0	10	2	6	5	7	7	8	6	7	3	8

Question; Legend for answers: Y-Yes, N-No, P-Partially		Slovenia	UK	Hungary	Poland	Malta	Cyprus	Portugal	Italy	France	Spain	Belgium	Greece	Romania	Netherlands
Q37	I am interested in studying degradation phenomena associated with the presence of metal ions in textiles.														
A	Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Y/N/P	Y	Y	P	Y	N	N	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	P	Y	Y
B	Do you have expertise to answer the question? Y/N/P	Y	Y	P	Y	N	N	Y	Y	N	Y	P	N	Y	Y
C	Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? 0 ..12	8	8	2	10	7	7	8	10	9	8	4	7	7	9
Q38	Study of mechanisms of degradation of dyes and organic colors. Development of stabilization strategies.														
A	Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Y/N/P	Y	Y	N	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y
B	Do you have expertise to answer the question? Y/N/P	Y	Y	N	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	P	N	Y	Y
C	Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? 0 ..13	9	6	0	10	5	9	8	5	9	7	10	7	8	9
Q39	I am interested in the possibilities of the combined use of the tomography and the dendrochronology as a pathway to dating wooden polychromed objects														
A	Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Y/N/P	Y	P	P	P	N	Y	Y	P	Y	Y	P	N	P	N
B	Do you have expertise to answer the question? Y/N/P	P	P	P	P	N	Y	Y	P	P	P	Y	N	N	P
C	Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? 0 ..14	5	8	5	10	6	9	7	9	10	6	10	6	7	
Q40	Evaluate the quantity or percentage of lost silver during cleaning and removing silver mirroring.														
A	Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Y/N/P	Y	Y	Y	P	N	N	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	P	Y
B	Do you have expertise to answer the question? Y/N/P	P	Y	Y	P	N	N	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	N	Y
C	Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? 0 ..15	6	5	9	7	6	6	5	5	6	8	0	5	6	9
Q41	What are the long-term effects of the use of cleaning gels on treated surfaces?														
A	Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Y/N/P	Y	P	N	P	N	N	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y
B	Do you have expertise to answer the question? Y/N/P	Y	P	N	P	N	N	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	P	Y
C	Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? 0 ..16	8	7	0	10	4	5	7	5	10	9	10	7	9	8
Q42	To what temperatures of fire were molten iron and bronze objects exposed (partially or completely) placed in the grave as a burnt offering?														
A	Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Y/N/P	Y	Y	P	N	N	N	N	P	P	Y	N	N	Y	P

Question; Legend for answers: Y-Yes, N-No, P-Partially		Slovenia	UK	Hungary	Poland	Malta	Cyprus	Portugal	Italy	France	Spain	Belgium	Greece	Romania	Netherlands
B	Do you have expertise to answer the question? Y/N/P	P	Y	Y	N	N	N	N	P	P	Y	N	N	P	P
C	Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? 0 ..17	7	5	3	10	4	7	7	8	9	6	0	6	8	10
Q43	I am interested in the relationship between selected stable isotopes (nitrogen, carbon, oxygen, strontium) in animal bones / teeth from archaeological sites to gain insight into the diet of these organisms, their geographical origin / migration, breeding policy, paleoenvironment etc.														
A	Can you answer the question using the existing services of the RI? Y/N/P	P	Y	Y	N	N	N	Y	P	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y
B	Do you have expertise to answer the question? Y/N/P	P	Y	Y	N	N	N	Y	P	P	Y	Y	Y	Y	P
C	Is the question relevant for potential joint research activities? 0 ..18	5	6	10	8	5	7	8	9	9	6	10	10	9	

Analysing the replies from providers of National Nodes it is evident that the research infrastructure and expertise exists to answer almost all research questions of E-RIHS users. Except for Q 32 (*I would like to use robots in the simple tasks of conservators (for example for digitalization, cleaning, etc.)*) partial research infrastructure and expertise exist in some countries and would require some new investments in infrastructure and expertise development in the future. Furthermore, some countries (UK, Poland and Italy) expressed high interest in the development of this topic.

A very important conclusion of this GAP analysis is also evident that even though research infrastructure and expertise exist to answer a specific users' question, there is further interest to deepen the knowledge and expertise in potential future joint research activities. The Figure 1 below shows ranking of users' questions according to providers' interest to further elaborate on specific topics.

Figure 1: Ranking of users' questions according to providers' interest.

Here is the list of the 5 most relevant user's research questions according to future E-RIHS providers:

Q2: *We need more models (damage functions) to link environmental data with material degradation and enable evidence-based environmental management.*

Q30: *How to develop non-destructive techniques which provide compositional stratigraphical information?*

Q14: *Glass and vitreous materials: I am interested in the analysis of altered areas of glass objects for studying specific corrosion phenomena.*

Q 43: *I am interested in the relationship between selected stable isotopes (nitrogen, carbon, oxygen, strontium) in animal bones / teeth from archaeological sites to gain insight into the diet of these organisms, their geographical origin / migration, breeding policy, paleo environment etc.*

Q 27: *I am interested in modelling dust and particulate pollution deposition on historic surfaces*

These collected data on the ranked users research questions/needs (Figure 1) can also serve as one of the starting points for the preparation of a strategy for smart investments in the European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science (E-RIHS) for a medium-term period spanning 5-10 years.

Annex 2: What is the Smart Specialisation Strategy and how it guides the 2021-2027 programming period

Smart Specialisation Strategies (S3) have been introduced as a key element of EU Cohesion Policy since the 2014-2020 programming period.

Inspired by a long-standing scientific and policy debate in the field of EU regional innovation policies, the idea of smart specialisation is about each region finding its own role within global economy through the identification of the unique characteristics and assets of territory, and the concentration of innovation investments in areas in which there are existing or potential competitive advantages (Foray et al., 2009).

The reformed 2014-2020 Cohesion Policy was characterised by a significant effort towards thematic concentration and, within this perspective, by a shift of resources towards the innovation goal (Thematic Objective TO.1 – *Strengthening research, technological development and innovation*). This choice has been especially strengthened by the adoption of smart specialisation as ex-ante conditionality for accessing European Structural and Investment Funds (ESIF). Namely, the development of a Research and Innovation Strategy for Smart Specialisation (RIS3), drafted and approved according to the standards proposed by the EU, became a necessary step in order to activate European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) resources related to innovation⁵².

According to the most authoritative definition “*national/regional Research and Innovation Strategies for Smart Specialisation are integrated, place-based economic transformation agendas that:*

- *Focus on a limited number of key national/regional priorities, challenges and needs;*
- *Build on each territory strengths, competitive advantages and potential for excellence;*
- *Are inspired by a wide concept of innovation, supporting technological as well as practice-based innovation;*
- *Get stakeholders fully involved and encourage innovation and experimentation, according to an inclusive policy making approach:*
- *Are evidence-based and include sound monitoring and evaluation systems”* (Foray et al., 2012).

RIS3 refer to a place-based, multi-level and innovative agenda meant to encourage the development of intelligently designed R&I policies by all Member States and Regions of the EU (Foray, 2015; OECD, 2013). Its introduction was intended to counter the trend towards converging, “photocopied” strategies and, instead, stimulate the emergence of original paths of development through distinctive pilot initiatives and “smart” experimentations, inspired by a wider concept of innovation.

The RIS3 agenda implementation is characterised by innovative governance requirements, related to the need to:

- Set up a dynamic and evolutionary prioritisation process in order to match research and innovation strengths with business needs and necessary skills, according to the so-called *Entrepreneurial Discovery Process* (EDP);

⁵² Regulation EU No 1303/2013.

- Be based on an inclusive strategy-making, possibly widening the range of stakeholders to include new actors that are usually not involved in the traditional consultation routines: not only industry, research institutions and Government exponents but also the demand side should be actively involved in the innovation process, according to the so-called *Quadruple Helix* (4H) model;
- Be outward-looking approach: outside connectivity entails both horizontal coordination among EU regions or local areas, in order to foster cross-border collaborations; and vertical multilevel coordination, by establishing explicit synergies between RIS3 and other EU and national policies and initiatives.

Over the 2021-2027 Cohesion Policy programming period, RIS3 are expected to continue to play a major role towards regional development and innovation policy. Particularly, *Good governance of national or regional smart specialisation strategy* is included as a thematic enabling condition within Policy Objective 1 (PO1) - *A smarter Europe: innovative & smart economic transformation*, focusing on seven fulfilment criteria, which cover the main success factors of RIS3 with respect to design, implementation and monitoring and evaluation mechanisms, i.e.:

1. *Up to date analysis of bottlenecks to innovation diffusion, including digitalization;*
2. *Existence of competent regional / national institution or body responsible for the management of S3;*
3. *Monitoring and evaluation tools to measure performance towards objectives of the strategy;*
4. *Effective functioning of the entrepreneurial discovery process;*
5. *Actions necessary to improve national or regional research and innovation systems;*
6. *Actions to manage industrial transition;*
7. *Measures for international collaboration opportunities*⁵³.

Under the ongoing programming period the RIS3 agenda is thus strengthened by good governance requirements: *“the governance process of smart specialisation is crucial for the quality of the strategy; the ERDF should provide support to developing and enhancing the capacities necessary for an efficient entrepreneurial discovery process and the preparation or updating of smart specialisation strategies*⁵⁴”.

Further elements strengthen the role that RIS3 will be playing under the 2021-2027 Cohesion Policy, namely:

- the provision that a percentage between 45% and 60% of the ROPs ERDF should be targeted to PO1, and therefore will be conditioned by the strategic guidelines represented by RIS3;
- the extension of the ERDF's operational scope to interventions supporting training and education related to the RIS3, industrial transition and entrepreneurship;
- the strengthening of the integrations between EU programs, recognizing RIS3 as a coherence tool for supporting investments in research and innovation (primarily between Initiatives financed by Structural Funds and Horizon Europe with the possible extension of this provision to other European instruments such as LIFE +, Erasmus +, Invest EU);

⁵³ Regulation EU No 1060/2021

⁵⁴ Regulation EU N.1058/2021

- the launch of the Interregional Innovation Investments initiative (I3), a new instrument proposed by the European Commission under the ERDF 2021-2027, with the aim of enhancing the RIS3 interregional cooperation logic⁵⁵.

⁵⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/2021-2027_en [visited on January 11, 2023]

Annex 3: Analysis of RIS3 at the EU level with specific reference to the countries and regions involved in E-RIHS

A first mapping of the 2021-2027 RIS3 of Countries and Regions involved in E-RIHS is here below proposed.

The analysis is conducted referring to the E-RIHS 14 founding members i.e.: Belgium, Cyprus, France, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Malta, The Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovenia, Spain and United Kingdom (Figure 1).

Two issues are highlighted for the purpose of this activity.

First, despite the heterogeneity of the polity context and the different regulatory frameworks that characterise EU States, a strong role in terms of S3 governance is played by the meso-levels of NUTS2 Region.⁵⁶ Since its introduction, Regions have had an overwhelming weight in defining and implementing RIS3, also due to the fact that the ERDF and the European Social Fund (ESF) Operational Programmes (OP) are usually managed by regional public authorities, responsible for their deployment. As a consequence, in most of the countries, national and regional strategies were designed and developed. The only exception is represented by “small” Member States, where national authorities have played that role (e.g., Malta and Cyprus).

Second, at the time of this document most of the 2021-2027 RIS3 have just been approved and the S3 Platform is currently not completely updated. The Platform, which was established ad hoc in 2011 by the European Commission for the purpose of offering support and facilitate transnational and trans-regional learning around RIS3, is hosted by the Joint Research Centre (JRC) Institute of Prospective Technological Studies (IPTS) of Seville (ES) and offers methodologies, tools, expertise and advice⁵⁷. Amongst these, a specific tool Eye @ RIS3 that visualises RIS3 investment priorities for innovation across EU regions and countries, thus representing a key database and source of information for the purpose of this analysis.

⁵⁶ The NUTS classification (Nomenclature of territorial units for statistics) is a hierarchical system for dividing up the economic territory for statistical and socio-economic analysis purposes. NUTS2 are basic regions for the application of regional policies, especially EU Cohesion Policy.

⁵⁷ s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu [visited on July 7, 2022]

Figure 1. E-RIHS founding members: National Node's coordinators

Appointed National Node's Coordinators			
	Country	National Node's Coordinator	Organization
	Belgium	Wim Fremout	Royal Institute for Cultural Heritage (KIK/IRPA)
	Cyprus	Sorin Hermon	The Cyprus Institute
	France	Victor Etgens	Centre de recherche et de restauration des musées de France, C2RMF
	Greece	Demetrios Anglos	Institute of Electronic Structure and Laser Foundation for Research and Technology-Hellas
	Hungary	Zita Szikszai	Institute for Nuclear Research
	Italy	Costanza Miliani	National Research Council of Italy (CNR)
	Malta	JoAnn Cassar	Deputy Dean, Faculty for the Built Environment, Head, Department of Conservation and Built Heritage, Faculty for the Built Environment, University of Malta
	Netherlands	Jan van't Hof	Rijksdienst voor Cultureel Erfgoed
	Poland	Piotr Targowski	Nicolaus Copernicus University in Toruń, Faculty of Physics, Astronomy and Informatics
	Portugal	Antonio Candeias	HERCULES Laboratory – Evora University
	Romania	Roxana RADVAN	National Institute of Research and Development for Optoelectronics INOE 2000
	Slovenia	Polonca Ropret	Institute for the Protection of Cultural Heritage of Slovenia (IPCHS); Slovene name: Zavod za varstvo kulturne dediščine (ZVKDS)
	Spain	Emilio Cano	Centro Nacional de Investigaciones Metalúrgicas (CENIM) PTI "Patrimonio Abierto: Investigación y Sociedad (PTI-PAIS) Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC)
	UK	May Cassar	Institute for Sustainable Heritage at University College London

The following table (Table 1) reports some first evidence.

For each E-RIHS National Nodes organization, the RIS3 selected domains are reported, considering the regional NUTS2 level territorial level, except for Malta and Cyprus, who developed a national RIS3.

As a first step, information includes the list of selected specialisations, where available on line. A deeper investigation of the Culture and Cultural Heritage linked RIS3 domains is undergoing as far as the Italian regions as pilot in order to understand more in depth their specific mission, goals and thematic clusters. This will be integrated by an investigation of the ERDF 2021-2027 Operational Programs and related financial allocations and measures in order to identify potential collaboration application areas at the local level.

Table 1. National/Regional RIS3 specialisation domains in E-RHIS founding members

E-RIHS National Nodes organisations	Country	NUTS2 Region	National/Regional RIS3 2021-2027 domains
Royal Institute for Cultural Heritage (KIK/IRPA)	Belgium	Région de Bruxelles-Capitale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advanced digital technologies & services • Climate: resilient buildings and infrastructure • Optimal use of resources • Efficient and sustainable urban flows for an inclusive management of urban space • Personalized and integrated Health & Care • Social innovation, public innovation and social inclusion
The Cyprus Institute	Cyprus		
Centre de recherche et de restauration des musées de France, C2RMF	France	Île-de-France (Paris)	
Institute of Electronic Structure and Laser Foundation for Research and Technology-Hellas	Greece	Crete	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agro-food value chain • Biosciences, health and pharmaceuticals • Digital technologies

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustainable energy • Environment and circular economy • Tourism, culture and creative industries
Institute for Nuclear Research	Hungary	Northern Great Plain region	
National Research Council of Italy (CNR)	Italy	Tuscany	<p><i>Technological priorities:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital technologies • Technologies for advanced manufacturing • Advanced materials and nanotechnologies; • Technologies for life and environment. <p><i>Application areas:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environment, Territory, Energy • Culture and Heritage • Health • Smart Agrifood • Intelligent and sustainable firm
		Lazio	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aerospace • Agri-food • Automotive and sustainable mobility • Sea economy • Green economy • Creative and digital industries • Cultural Heritage and technologies for culture • Life science • Security
		Campania	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aerospace • Biotechnologies, health, and agritech • Cultural heritage, creative industries and tourism • Energy, environment, sustainable buildings • Transport and logistics

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New materials and enabling technologies • Blue growth • Fashion (Made in Italy and design)
Deputy Dean, Faculty for the Built Environment, Head, Department of Conservation and Built Heritage, Faculty for the Built Environment, University of Malta	Malta		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Health and well-being • Sustainable use of resources for climate change mitigation and adaptation • Smart manufacturing • Marine & maritime technology. • Aviation and aerospace • Future digital technologies
Rijksdienst voor Cultureel Erfgoed	The Netherlands	Amersfoort in the province of Utrecht, West Netherlands region	
Nicolaus Copernicus University in Toruń, Faculty of Physics, Astronomy and Informatics	Poland	City of Toruń in the Kuyavian-Pomerania region	
HERCULES Laboratory – Evora University	Portugal	City of Évora, Alentejo region	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustainable bioeconomy • Sustainable energy • Mobility and Logistics • Tourism and Hospitality services • Cultural and creative ecosystem • Social innovation and citizenship
National Institute of Research and Development for Optoelectronics INOE 2000	Romania	City of Măgurele , Muntenia region	
Institute for the Protection of Cultural Heritage of Slovenia (IPCHS) <i>Slovene name: Zavod za varstvo kulturne dediščine</i>	Slovenia	Central Slovenia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Smart buildings and homes including the Wood Chain • Smart cities and communities • ICT - KETs and horizontal areas

(ZVKDS)			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Networks for the transition into circular economy • Health and medicine • Sustainable mobility • Factories of the future • Sustainable food production • Sustainable tourism • Development of materials as products
<p>Centro Nacional de Investigaciones Metalúrgicas (CENIM)</p> <p>PTI "Patrimonio Abierto: Investigación y Sociedad (PTI-PAIS)</p> <p>Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC)</p>	Spain	Community of Madrid	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Human and social Processes • Communications and digital transformation • Enabling advanced technologies • Ecological transition • Global health • Biotechnology and agri-food
Institute for Sustainable Heritage at University College London	UK		

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